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Digital Humanities and Digital Knowledge**

What do we mean by “data” in the arts and humanities?

**Final Dissertation in
Open Science**

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Abstract

We describe here the interviews we conducted in late 2021 with 1 representative for each of the 19 disciplinary areas within the department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies (FICLIT) at the University of Bologna. The answers we gathered from participants were analysed using the Grounded Theory method and allowed us to reflect on the definition of the word “data” in the humanities domain, what research materials should be considered to fall within this definition, and what researchers in this field think of the term. In addition, we gathered information on other aspects of research, such as methodologies, possible copyright and privacy concerns, preservation strategies, and more.

First, we extracted a list of 16 research materials that constitute the “building blocks” of research in the humanities, as far as our interviewees are concerned; publications emerged as the most important one. The majority of participants included most of the materials they use in research within their definition of data, and this term did not seem to be especially problematic for them, contrary to what has been reported elsewhere. Most researchers also stated they have a precise methodology, although rarely formalised, which is surprising when compared to the available literature. Regarding data management practices, our results mostly confirm what emerged from previous studies, but collaboration was a notable exception: sharing with colleagues, and teamwork appear more common than reported elsewhere. Finally, the attitudes towards open science and open data are mostly positive among the interviewees.

The study should be replicated on a larger scale, and include other disciplines, to confirm these findings and paint a more precise picture of how research is done in the humanities and how it can be made more FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable).

1. Introduction

The term **open scholarship** has been described by J. Tennant, J.E. Beamer, J. Bosman et al. to “broadly refer to the process, communication, and re-use of research as practised in any scholarly research discipline, and its inclusion and role within wider society”. It is closely linked to the concepts of open access, open data, and open evaluation, and builds on a number of documents and declarations published over the previous 2 decades, such as the Budapest Open Access Initiative, The Open Archives Initiative, and others (Tennant et al. 2019, p. 14). According to the authors, the term open scholarship, less common than the term open science, is however more inclusive:

[...] the word ‘Science’ [...] can have an adverse effect of excluding researchers from the arts, humanities, engineering, mathematics, and other fields that might not be considered to be science. (*ibidem*, p. 18)

They note that languages other than English may not present this semantic problem¹. The issue, however, does resonate with Italian speakers.

The beginning of this discussion around widening public access to research can be traced back to the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI)² that, in a 2002 declaration, defined for the first time the term **open access**:

The literature that should be freely accessible online is that which scholars give to the world without expectation of payment. [...]. By “open access” to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, pass them as data to software, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers other than those inseparable from gaining access to the internet itself. (Chan et al. 2002)

Other declarations followed suit³, broadening the definition to also include:

research results, raw data and metadata, source materials, digital representations of pictorial and graphical materials and scholarly multimedia material. (Max Planck Society 2003)

With focus shifting away from publication and towards all research materials, the terms **open science** and **open data** were born.

The European Union’s Research & Innovation (R&I) policy has embraced these concepts as pillars of the European Research Area (ERA)⁴. The new ERA policy agenda for the period 2022-2024 sets a number of concrete actions, the first of which is to “enable open science,

¹ Think, for example, of the term “wissenschaft” in German (*ibidem*).

² <https://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read/>

³ See particularly the Bethesda Statement on Open Access Publishing (2003), <http://legacy.earlham.edu/~peters/fos/bethesda.htm> and the Berlin Declaration on Open Access to Knowledge in the Sciences and Humanities (2003), <https://openaccess.mpg.de/Berlin-Declaration>.

⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/research-and-innovation/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/our-digital-future/era_en#documents

including through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)” (European Commission 2022). The EOSC⁵ is an EU-funded project⁶ to provide:

European researchers, innovators, companies and citizens with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes (EOSC 2022).

The EOSC portal⁷, very much still a work in progress, is aimed at strengthening the ERA and developing a “web of FAIR data and services for science in Europe” (EOSC 2022).

FAIR is an acronym for **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable** and the concept was first introduced in a 2016 article published on *Scientific Data*. Noting that “science funders, publishers and governmental agencies are beginning to require data management and stewardship plans for data generated in publicly funded experiments” the authors describe the rationale researchers should follow in the management of scientific data (Wilkinson et al. 2016).

In this scenario, the exact meaning of the word **data** is increasingly being discussed within the scholarly community, as we will see in detail in [section 2](#). The use of this term, and the application of FAIR principles, within the art and humanities domain, however, is not without problems. As pointed out, among others, by E. Tóth-Czifra:

[...] by applying the FAIR data guiding principles to arts and humanities data curation workflows, it will be uncovered that contrary to their general scope and deliberately domain-independent nature, they have been implicitly designed according to underlying assumptions about how knowledge creation operates and communicates (Tóth Czifra 2019, p. 3).

In the same instance, the author calls for:

Iterated and large-scale surveys [...] to assess whether and to what extent the term data is still a dirty word in the increasingly digital humanities disciplines and how the evolving landscape of Open data and FAIR data policies impact and transform such conceptions of data (*ibidem*, p. 15).

The present work is a small contribution towards this goal and follows other surveys and interviews involving university staff at different levels, across different disciplines and in different countries (please see [section 2.6](#)).

⁵ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

⁶ First in the context of Horizon 2020 and currently of Horizon Europe.

⁷ The EOSC is organised “along disciplines and epistemic traditions” and the humanities are represented through the thematic Social Sciences and Humanities cluster of the EOSC, or SSHOC (Tóth Czifra and Barbot 2021).

Although the scale of this project is limited, it has allowed us to answer 3 main research questions:

1. If we want to implement FAIR principles in our respective fields, **how do we define the word “data” in the humanities?** What research materials should be considered as data?
2. **What do researchers think of the word “data”?** Is it problematic for them?
3. More generally, what are the attitudes towards open data and open science?

Hopefully our analysis, which also covers current research practices and especially methodologies, possible copyright and privacy concerns, preservation strategies, and more, will contribute to the growing body of research that is looking for the best way forward for FAIR data principles within the arts and humanities domain, without relying on assumptions drawn from other disciplines.

If we want to ensure that our disciplines are represented within the increasingly digital scholarly ecosystem, and within the EOSC, we must develop methods and infrastructures based on a **clear understanding of the nature of humanities research**, its peculiarities, its strengths, and its weaknesses. As J. Edmond puts it in the introduction to her 2020 edited volume *Digital Technology and the Practices of Humanities Research*,

The prospect of the requirement that all funded European researchers deposit their data in an open repository for reuse by others forces us to face a host of questions that would have otherwise lain unresolved. [...] What are the new data streams and sets that humanists create? Should paradata be more formally captured during the research process, and if so, how do we untangle it from the uniquely formed scholarly instrument of the individual humanist so as to make such data epistemically available to others? (Edmond, 2020, p. 6)

The [next section](#) will delve deeper on the topics touched in this introduction, presenting an overview of data definitions across different research fields. In [section 3](#) we will describe the methodology used in this project, from organising the interviews to analysing the answers received. [Section 4](#) presents the main results of our analysis in a schematic fashion, while [section 5](#) discusses all of them in detail.

2. Literature review

2.1 Open access and open science: terminology

As mentioned, the discussion around widening public access to research can be traced back to the Budapest Open Access Initiative (BOAI), a statement of principle, strategy and commitment signed by representatives of researchers, universities, laboratories, libraries, foundations, journals, publishers, learned societies (Chan et al. 2002). In it, we find a single mention of the word “data” (here and below, the bold is mine):

By “open access” to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, **pass them as data to software**, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers. (Chan et al. 2002)

The focus, at that point in time, was on opening access to “peer-reviewed journal literature”, slightly broadened a few lines below in “literature [...] which scholars give to the world without expectation of payment” (*ibidem*) to include other scholarly outputs such as monographs, or conference proceedings. Interestingly, these publications are considered data in the context of text mining.

In the so-called BOAI10, the declaration released 10 years later as part of the same initiative, the definition of **open access** is mostly unchanged, but the authors mention the need for open tools:

The list of essential tools will evolve over time, but includes OA repositories and journals, free and open-source repository software, free and open-source journal management software, tools for text- and data-mining [...]. (Abraham et al. 2012)

while in section 3 the idea is introduced that articles and monographs might have “underlying data”:

We encourage experiments with new forms of the scholarly research “article” and “book” in which **texts are integrated in useful ways with underlying data**, multimedia elements, executable code, related literature, and user commentary. (*ibidem*)

Finally, section 4 contains the first, quite generic, mention of “research data”:

The worldwide campaign for OA to research articles should work more closely with the worldwide campaigns for OA to books, theses and dissertations, **research data, government data, educational resources, and source code**. (*ibidem*)

This progression from opening access to scientific publications, as the main output of research, to include infrastructures and underlying data reflects a more general shift in attitudes within the research community.

The term **open science** is often preferred today, as this shift was led by the so-called STEM disciplines⁸, where the case for unfettered access to research data is perhaps more immediate and easier to argue⁹. The European Union, for example, uses this term both in official documents¹⁰ and in publicity materials¹¹ (bold in the original):

The challenge is for Europe **to embrace open science as the modus operandi for all researchers**. Open science consists in the sharing of knowledge, data and tools as early as possible in the Research and Innovation (R&I) process, in open collaboration with all relevant knowledge actors, including academia, industry, public authorities, end users, citizens and society at large. Open science has the potential to increase the quality, efficiency and impact of R&I, lead to greater responsiveness to societal challenges, and increase trust of society in the science system. (Directorate-General R&I 2021)

In this same document open science is defined as the intersection between open access to **research outputs, defined as “publications, data, software, models, algorithms, and workflows”**, use of open research infrastructures, and promotion of open peer-review and open collaboration (Directorate-General R&I 2021). Transparency is required though the entire research process, and publications are mentioned alongside data and workflows as different types of research output.

Other terms, such as open humanities (Knöchelmann 2019) or open scholarship (Tennant et al. 2019), have been suggested but did not yet reach as widespread an adoption as the term open science¹².

2.2 The arts and humanities perspective

We have already touched upon the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)¹³, and its aim to be “a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment” where to “publish, find and re-use data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes” (European Commission 2022). Social science and humanities disciplines (SSH) cannot risk being underrepresented¹⁴ within the EOSC since

Achieving interoperability with the larger Open Science and technical framework of the EOSC is key to connecting the SSH data landscape with discipline-agnostic scholarly information management systems that are used or will be used for discovery or for assessment of scholars’ work. (Tóth Czifra and Barbot 2021²)

⁸ STEM stands for Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics.

⁹ See, e.g., Yozwiak (2015).

¹⁰ Such as, e.g., <https://op.europa.eu/s/vMYv>

¹¹ See, e.g., <https://op.europa.eu/s/vMYt>

¹² See <https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?date=all&q=open%20scholarship,open%20science>, quoted from Tennant et al. (2019, p. 18).

¹³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

¹⁴ Of the 323 resources available on the main EOSC page on February 10, 2022, 21 are listed under the Humanities scientific domain. See <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

The thematic Social Sciences and Humanities cluster of the EOSC, called SSHOC¹⁵, is working towards facilitating “the social sciences, humanities, and heritage science contribution to the EOSC” by interconnecting infrastructures, maximising data reuse, providing training and setting up appropriate governance models (SSHOC 2022).

The EOSC is based on the so-called FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) data principles and GO FAIR¹⁶ is the “bottom-up, stakeholder-driven and self-governed initiative” aimed at implementing these principles. It has several implementation networks, among which we find CO-OPERAS IN¹⁷, whose objective is to (the bold is mine):

[...] help the social sciences and humanities (SSH) communities making their data and publications Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR). This FAIRification process is essential to build a bridge between SSH data and the EOSC, **widening the concept of “research data” to include all of the types of digital research output linked to scholarly communication that are part of the research process.** (OPERAS 2022)

Among the activities they promote to reach this goal, we find literature reviews on the definitions of “data”, the identification of standards used by the SSH communities and surveys of SSH needs, challenges, and practices regarding FAIRification (OPERAS 2022).

It may be useful to stress here that, although FAIR principles and open science often go in tandem, “FAIR is not equal to Open”:

The FAIR principles, although inspired by Open Science, explicitly and deliberately do not address moral and ethical issues pertaining to the openness of data. In the envisioned Internet of FAIR Data and Services, the degree to which any piece of data is available, or even advertised as being available (via its metadata) is entirely at the discretion of the data owner. (Mons et al. 2017, p. 51)

Privacy and security issues may legitimately prevent researchers to give public access to some types of data, while “clarity and transparency around the conditions governing access and reuse” must still be granted – this, ad not openness, is the core of FAIR data principles (Mons et al. 2017).

¹⁵ <https://sshopencloud.eu/sshoc-eosc>

¹⁶ <https://www.go-fair.org/>

¹⁷ <https://www.go-fair.org/implementation-networks/overview/co-operas/>

2.3 Defining “data”

How are data defined in the literature? In this section we will look at some examples, to try and understand what kind of research materials should be included in a definition that works well for the humanities domain.

But first, let us briefly look at the article that introduced the concept of FAIR data. Interestingly, it does not contain any explicit definition of data, but several passages allow us to deduce one:

Importantly, it is our intent that the principles apply not only to “data” in the conventional sense, but also to the algorithms, tools, and workflows that led to that data. All scholarly digital research objects—from data to analytical pipelines—benefit from application of these principles, since all components of the research process must be available to ensure transparency, reproducibility, and reusability. (Wilkinson et al. 2016, p. 1)

According to this quote, algorithms, tools, and workflows are not considered as data. The authors continue:

There are numerous and diverse stakeholders who stand to benefit from overcoming these obstacles: researchers wanting to share, get credit, and reuse each other’s data and interpretations; professional data publishers offering their services; software and tool-builders [...]. (*ibidem*, p. 1)

We will see that this **distinction between “data and interpretations”** will emerge elsewhere in the literature and will be also reflected in the answers we received during the interviews we carried out as part of this project. However, let us note in passing that at least a third of researchers in our cohort did not see data as opposed to interpretation (for an in-depth analysis, see [section 5.9](#)).

The authors of this article also attempt a definition of **“non-data research objects”, such as “analytical workflows”** (Wilkinson et al. 2016), but they ultimately make these theoretical distinctions redundant when they state that:

The FAIR principles can equally be applied to these non-data assets, which need to be identified, described, discovered, and reused in much the same manner as data. (*ibidem*, p. 5)

2.3.1 The ALLEA report on FAIR data sharing in the humanities

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities and represents more than 50 institutions across 40 countries, both inside and outside the EU. Its “Sustainable and FAIR Data Sharing in the Humanities” report, penned by the Working Group on E-Humanities¹⁸, states that the **definition of data encompasses all inputs and outputs of research that are not publications:**

¹⁸ The working group has used the following methodology in drafting these guidelines: “surveying reports published by the European Commission, seeking out future directions articulated by the projects and groups

In defining research data, we consider all inputs and outputs to the research process and distinguish data from research publications. (Harrower, Maryl et al. 2020, p. 6)

They underline the importance of a discipline-specific approach to FAIR principles (“the development of data sharing cultures and methods generally starts with disciplines”) and provide a set of recommendations to humanities scholars, “with the understanding that the humanities themselves are diverse and data practices and demands vary significantly” (*ibidem*).

They identify these key phases in the data management lifecycle in the humanities: (i) identify data, (ii) plan, (iii) collect/produce & structure & store, (iv) deposit for preservation, cite & share and finally (v) disseminate.

As far as identification is concerned, they note that some disciplines, like social sciences or anthropology, have long traditions of data-driven research, while others show a certain resistance towards the term “data”¹⁹ (*ibidem*). Here data are defined as follows (the bold is mine):

We could then define data in the humanities broadly as **all materials and assets scholars collect, generate and use during all stages of the research cycle** (*ibidem*, p. 8)²⁰.

And later they add:

[...] **we may also think of objects**, the primary focus of scholarly inquiry, **as our research data**. Possible study objects used in the humanities, in both physical and digital form, may include **historical artefacts, digital (incl. digitised) documents, images (2D or 3D), sound and video recordings**. (*ibidem*, p. 8)

These “objects” can be further enriched by scholars through “interpretations of their features in the form of annotations”²¹ (*ibidem*). So, once again, we find **a separation between data** (which include physical and digital cultural objects) **and their interpretation**.

When covering collection/production, structuring and storing, the report categorises data along these lines:

- **primary and secondary data**, the former collected first-hand, the latter already existing:

building the EOSC [...] and noting statements and activities on research data from relevant networks, such as DARIAH, CLARIN, OPERAS, the SHAPE-ID project, and the Research Data Alliance (RDA)”. After a first draft, they: “[...] ran an open consultation process over the period of two months to gather broad feedback from humanities researchers. [...] The open consultation received over 200 comments and editing suggestions, which were each carefully considered, and used to develop the final version of the recommendations” (Harrower, Maryl et al. 2020, p. 4).

¹⁹ They cite Edmond and Tóth-Czifra (2018).

²⁰ This definition (Harrower, Maryl et al. 2020, p. 8) seems to include publications, but we should keep in mind they have previously been excluded (*ibidem*, p. 6).

²¹ Examples given are XML mark-up, but also footnotes or critical commentary.

Different disciplines may employ different data types, but also different typologies. The collection typology, for instance, distinguishes between primary data, requested and collected by a researcher through first-hand research (e.g. experiment, survey, observation, text-mining), and secondary data, or resources which already exist and could become the subject of analysis (e.g. texts, objects, descriptions). (*ibidem*, p. 14)

- **quantitative and qualitative data:**

The former concerns the data that could be expressed in a numerical form (both continuous or discrete), [...]. The latter can usually be expressed in language to denote a certain quality of the object or its description [...]. (*ibidem*, p. 14)

Further, “data types” may be distinguished “by the basic media they use, i.e. word, image, sound, or the combination of these” or according to their structure (e.g., structured, semi-structured, and unstructured or, alternatively, linear, hierarchical or multi-relational) (*ibidem*).

Interestingly, only a couple of paragraphs are devoted to dissemination. They touch briefly upon publications and encourage researchers to “talk about [...] research outside academia [...] promoting the involvement of a wider audience in scientific research” (*ibidem*, p. 32).

We have seen how the ALLEA report **explicitly excludes publications from the definition of data**. This is not uncommon, and it might originally stem from a desire to move attention away from publications, which were the focus of the first conceptualisations within the open access/open science movement²², and towards “the full diversity of outputs”. Indeed,

In the 21st century, traditional publications and journal articles are far from being the only significant contributions to the advancement of knowledge. (Directorate-General R&I 2018, p. 11)

However, now that the discourse around FAIR data principles seems has brought all the other “significant contributions to the advancement of knowledge” into focus, and rightly so, this distinction between data and publications seems to have stayed with us²³. But is this distinction productive, especially in the humanities? Should not we **include scholarly publications in the definition of research data, within the FAIR framework?**

Texts and documents, after all, are data: many research projects in the humanities, especially but not exclusively in philology and literary criticism, revolve around the study of texts and

²² See [section 2.1](#) above.

²³ Just to give an example, L. Waltman, in his blog post “Publications should be FAIR”, argues that “Scholarly data sets are increasingly expected to be FAIR [...]. To fully realize the benefits of open access to the scholarly literature [...] publications should be FAIR as well”. He adds that open access to the scholarly literature has stressed accessibility and reusability at the expenses of findability and interoperability (Waltman 2020). Here, too, the distinction is made between data, on the one hand, and publications, on the other (although, interestingly, he uses the term “data sets” rather than “data”).

documents²⁴. They belong, no doubt, to those “materials and assets scholars collect, generate and use” (Harrower, Maryl et al. 2020, p. 8). Indeed, the ALLEA report explicitly states that both texts and documents are data²⁵. So why are we excluding scholarly publications?

Is it the act of publishing that strips texts of their status as data? Or are we considering only non-contemporary texts and documents as data? Both these statements are of course indefensible, or we should argue that scholars interested in contemporary novels are not working with data, while scholars interested in unpublished Medieval texts are. Using official publication (whatever we mean by that) to distinguish whether a certain text can be considered data, or not, is simply not correct in our opinion.

Or are we making this distinction because scholarly publications contain an interpretation? Then we should claim that scholars studying the academic work of other scholars (e.g., Sigmund Freud, or Umberto Eco) are not working with data, while the others are. We can probably all agree that scholarly publications, such as books or articles, while **constituting the output of the research process, can also be the input for new research**. It may be argued that new research is not based on the existing publications, but rather on the underlying data that are “embodied” in those publications.

This is perhaps sustainable within STEM disciplines, admitting that the methodology is also included in the definition of underlying data, but it does not make much sense in the context of humanities disciplines. For example, think about a situation in which a published text is used, as part of a wider corpus, to study a certain linguistic phenomenon; or one in which a researcher is looking at the form that bibliographic citations take within a certain discipline. In these contexts, are we not using publications, in their final, crystallised form, as data for new research? Even the BOAI declaration contains the description of such a case (the bold is mine):

By “open access” to this literature, we mean its free availability on the public internet, permitting any users to read, download, copy, distribute, print, search, or link to the full texts of these articles, crawl them for indexing, **pass them as data to software**, or use them for any other lawful purpose, without financial, legal, or technical barriers. (Chan et al. 2002)

If we look at the way our interviewees at FICLIT described their research, **publications emerge as the most important type of data in the humanities**, both in terms of research output, but also in terms of input, be it primary or secondary sources (see [section 5.2](#)).

²⁴ Whether the focus is on the text, or the document is non inconsequential for these scholars, but unfortunately this is out of the scope of the present discussion.

²⁵ As stated in these passages, also quoted above: “primary data, [...] and secondary data, or resources which already exist and could become the subject of analysis (e.g. texts, objects, descriptions)”; and “we may also think of objects, the primary focus of scholarly inquiry, as our research data. Possible study objects used in the humanities, in both physical and digital form, may include historical artefacts, digital (incl. digitised) documents [...]” (Harrower, Maryl et al. 2020).

We will see over the next sections that this position, that publications should be considered data within the FAIR framework, has been argued elsewhere, for example in the context of the GO FAIR initiative, and the OPERAS research infrastructure.

2.3.2 *The many definitions emerged from the CO-OPERAS IN workshops*

When we introduced the GO FAIR initiative, we mentioned that its CO-OPERAS Implementation Network is interested in widening the definition of data to better fit the humanities point of view. For this purpose, they organised 5 workshops in Italy, Portugal, Germany, France and Belgium in 2019-2020, and gathered more than 70 researchers from 32 different humanities and social sciences disciplines²⁶. The reports give us some interesting insights.

During the first workshop, some researchers defined data as a process and expression of a method, which makes metadata and “paradata” (data describing the methods of data generation) crucial. In addition, **books and articles can be data as they can constitute the basis for new research** (CO-OPERAS & Giglia 2020¹). As we have seen, we certainly agree with this last point.

Many participants to the second meeting seemed to agree on the fact that raw data do not make sense because **data acquire meaning through context and use**. They also concluded that there are many definitions of data, according to the disciplinary area, and that it is **almost impossible to find a definition on which everybody can agree** (CO-OPERAS & Borges 2020).

The participants to the third workshop, held in Germany²⁷, confirmed that “there is a broader diversity of conceptions on what constitutes data in the SSH” (CO-OPERAS, Bertino, Tóth-Czifra 2020). The report also remarks that (bold in the original):

In several contexts, we saw a certain degree of **reluctance towards the term ‘data’: some scholars claim that they do not work with ‘data’**, but with texts, images, etc. This scepticism seemed to be especially prevalent in disciplines adopting often hermeneutic approaches. For these scholars, the term data carries an expression of objectifying and a forceful application of methods, vocabulary and

²⁶ Researchers were asked to answer the question “What are data in the Humanities?” and to assess the FAIRness of their current data practices, after listening to a presentation on the nature of the CO-OPERAS IN project. The workshops covered the following disciplines: “Archaeology, Archives (Art history), Botany, Chemistry, Classical studies (Latin literature), Communication Science, Compared literature, Cultural Heritage, Digital Humanities, Economy, Ethnology, French literature, Hindology, History, History of Philosophy, International Law, Library and Information Science, Linguistics, Literature, Musicology, Philology, Philosophy, Portuguese Studies, Sociology” (Avanço, Giglia, Gingold 2021).

²⁷ Co-organised by CO-OPERAS and SSHOC, the first part had a very similar structure to the previous workshops, while the second was aimed at gathering “feedback and demands of the participants towards the SSH Open Marketplace” (CO-OPERAS, Bertino, Tóth-Czifra 2020).

narratives of the natural sciences, which is in principle foreign to them. (CO-OPERAS, Bertino, Tóth-Czifra 2020, p. 2)

It is therefore necessary to “recognize that there is no unified, cross-disciplinary definition of data and that data is also a construct” and that “a FAIR data management should probably include a clarification or at least guidelines **to clarify the conditions under which certain data can be considered as data** in a specific research project” (*ibidem*). The lack of incentives for data curation and the “publish or perish” mentality emerged as the main challenges to FAIRification in the humanities (*ibidem*). These aspects also emerged, although perhaps not as strongly, in the interviews we carried out at FICLIT.

During the fourth meeting, held in France²⁸, participants stressed the major problems posed by data accessibility, and that **data openness and GDPR provisions about anonymisation appear contradictory**. They asked: “is data fully anonymised fully reusable?”. The idea that “data [...] is never ‘raw data’”, emerged here, too (CO-OPERAS 2020).

The final meeting²⁹, which had the purpose of summarising the opinions on data emerged from the other events, concluded that:

- there is no consensus on what data in the humanities is;
- any definition has to “consider the process of data production, going as deep as possible in research practices” and be “linked to the workflow of knowledge creation”;
- a “focus on digital/analogical similarities and divergences” would be helpful (CO-OPERAS & Giglia 2020², p. 1).

Although the idea that publications are data emerged from some of the CO-OPERAS IN workshops, this point did not make it into the final summative report. The document goes on to stress the importance of researchers’ engagement and training, for example through disciplinary workshops and data journals to “increase interest [...] and give publicity to projects that try to produce and publish FAIR data” (*ibidem*, p. 3).

Many of the statements found in the CO-OPERAS IN reports also emerged during our interviews at FICLIT. For example, privacy concerns are indeed a major obstacle for data

²⁸ The structure of the workshop was very similar to the Turin and Coimbra ones. In this case, the audience included technical experts and “rather than defining the concept of data, the participants discussed very practical issues ranging from data sharing workflows, work environment organization, institutional policies and incentive” (CO-OPERAS 2020).

²⁹ This was a meeting of experts convened to evaluate what had emerged from previous the workshops and to make a statement regarding FAIRification strategies in the SSH.

sharing, especially in a research area such as language and linguistics, which tends to deal with personal data³⁰ more often than, e.g., philology and literary studies (see [section 5.6](#)).

However, although some scholars in our cohort did claim that they do not work with data, this position was taken only by 2 researchers, while 13 stated that they did³¹. Indeed, when we asked interviewees to define the term “data”, we also noticed a **multitude of definitions and a lack of agreement**. Most of the definitions we collected tended to include different research materials in the definition, while only a small minority (3) – interestingly, all language and linguistics scholars – considered them exclusively as “raw data”³²(see [section 5.8](#)).

2.3.4 OPERAS-P reports on innovative approach to SSH FAIR data and on the future of scholarly communication

Another interesting document for this discussion is the OPERAS-P³³ “Report on innovative approach to SSH FAIR data and publications”. The authors worked in synergy with the CO-OPERAS IN, and the conclusions of this report, which is still a draft, are partly based on the results of the workshops we described above (Avanço, Giglia, Gingold 2021, pp. 5-9).

They also conducted a literature review “to investigate the definition of data in the SSH context”³⁴ from which emerged that the term, born with the scientific revolution and empirical science, changed its meaning with the advent of digital technology (bold is mine):

The intersection between information science and technology has changed the status and the meaning of data: anything that can be transposed into binary bits constitutes data that in turn feeds and supports the entire digital environment. **At first strictly scientific as a concept and a practice, data became informational, with a wider meaning now ranging from knowledge to technology.** (Avanço, Giglia, Gingold 2021, p. 7)

The result of this shift is that “every informational data is technically data” and that “every data can potentially be also scientific data, even if not always immediately” (*ibidem*, p. 8).

The report goes on to make recommendations for the implementation of FAIR data principles in the humanities and social sciences, with a particular focus on SSH specificities

³⁰ For a definition of personal data see: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/what-personal-data_en

³¹ The total number of interviewees was 19. In addition, 3 responded they were unsure and 1 did not respond directly to the question.

³² Although they used expressions such as “information items”, “raw materials”, or “quantitative components”.

³³ Both OPERAS-P and the CO-OPERAS IN belong to the OPERAS Research Infrastructure, an EU-funded project for the development of open scholarly communication in the social sciences and humanities: <https://operas.hypotheses.org/>.

³⁴ They analysed 28 open access publications, in English and French, all but one published after 2008 (Avanço, Giglia, Gingold 2021, p. 6).

such as multilingualism and “bibliodiversity”, which need to be preserved, and on the creation of research-driven infrastructures. They also mention the need to standardise methods “so they can be univocally recalled” (*ibidem*, pp. 13-14).

The document consistently uses the expression “SSH data and publications”, **indicating that they are considerate separate, but ultimately equivalent from a FAIR perspective.**

The intersection between these two concepts was reportedly also explored during an event held by the group in February 2021, about the future of scholarly communication, where the topic “publications as data” was discussed both with a panel of experts and with the participants.

The experts confirmed the uncertain status of data in general, [...]. In the SSH, in particular, the hybrid landscape (both digital and non-digital) and the importance of publications, with their specific legal status, makes it difficult to apply the concept of data uniformly. Therefore, the suggestion was to start the FAIRification process from the existing practices and identify potential convergences with the generic FAIR principles (*ibidem*, p. 17).

So, while confirming the importance of publications in the humanities, the aim is ultimately to “move from a definition of data based on data types and disciplines to the management of objects related to specific communities and aims” (*ibidem*, p. 9).

If this report shies away from defining publications as data, another wide-ranging document, stemming from the February 2021 event we just mentioned, does just that. The OPERAS “Report on the Future of Scholarly Communication” (Avanço, Balula et al. 2021) states that, **within the FAIR framework, everything is data, or could be**, with the concept of data “**intended to be as universal as possible, including datasets, publications, software, etc.**” (*ibidem*, p. 22). They also describe some of the main challenges ahead:

- FAIR awareness is still low in SSH;
- there is great diversity and complexity in the SSH research environment;
- it is necessary to work on incentives and rewards mechanisms (*ibidem*, p. 23).

The report deals with many other aspects of the scholarly communication ecosystem, aside from FAIR data, including innovative models in scholarly publications and the future of scholarly writing. They note, for example, that in the sciences there is a “timely reporting of facts through journal articles, while the humanities value the depth and breadth of the interpretation conveyed by a monograph”³⁵ (*ibidem*, p. 34).

³⁵ This point is also made in a 2015 report to the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE), where “monographs, and other longer research publications such as edited books, scholarly editions and exhibition catalogues” were described as offering “the space needed to set out arguments and evidence in disciplines where that is necessary, complementing the importance of articles in learned journals. Monographs are not, however, simply a means of communicating research findings. The process of constructing and writing a book is often a core way to shape the ideas, structure the argument, and work out the relationship

2.4 Beyond data: digital objects and research objects

2.4.1 The FAIR digital object

In the 2018 document “Turning FAIR into reality: Final report and action plan from the European Commission expert group on FAIR data” the tension between data and publications seems to be resolved through the FAIR Digital Object:

[It] may represent data, software or other research resources. These digital objects must be accompanied by persistent identifiers, metadata and contextual documentation to enable discovery, citation and reuse. Data should also be accompanied by the code used to process and analyse the data. (Directorate-General R&I 2018, p. 8)

The report states explicitly, although in a footnote, that “**the FAIR principles do not just apply to data but to other digital objects including outputs of research**” (Directorate-General R&I 2018, p. 8, fn. 1).

Interestingly, the 2020 report from ALLEA that we have covered in [section 2.3.1](#) cites the FAIR digital object and describes it as “an elemental ‘bundle’” including “research data, persistent identifier, and rich metadata” (Harrower, Maryl et al. 2020, p. 17). However, it seems to regard it mainly as a technical solution, while the mention of the “other digital objects including outputs of research” has disappeared.

Figure 2.1: The FAIR digital object (Directorate-General R&I 2018, p. 35)

between these and the evidence that has emerged from the research process. At their best, monographs provoke debate, can shift paradigms, and provide a focal point for research” (Crossick 2015).

The “Turning FAIR into reality” report also invites research communities to work on the definitions surrounding FAIR, according to the “data types” specific to their discipline:

In order to implement FAIR, research communities must define how the FAIR principles and related concepts apply in their context. This will differ based on the data types, the nature of research (e.g. ethical sensitivities or commercial partners) and the level of existing support for data sharing. (Directorate-General R&I 2018, p. 8)

Their recommendations are organised around 3 main steps:

- Step 1: Define – concepts for FAIR Digital Objects and the ecosystem,
- Step 2: Implement – culture, technology and skills for FAIR practice,
- Step 3: Embed and sustain – incentives, metrics and investment³⁶ (*ibidem*, p. 8).

2.4.2 The Research Object

Another useful concept that, again, seems to resolve the semantic complexities of the term “data” is that of the Research Object (RO)³⁷ (Bechhofer et al. 2013). From the eScience lab we learn that (bold is mine):

The useful **outcomes of research are not just traditional publications. Instead they are everything else that goes into, and supports an investigation.** [...] “Research Objects” describes a number of initiatives and approaches trying to describe and associate all of this content together in a machine-readable mechanism so that it can be more easily shared and exchanged (eScience Lab 2022).

This approach is based on 3 core principles: (i) identity (using unique identifiers such as DOIs for publications or ORCID IDs for researchers), (ii) aggregation and (iii) annotation (use of complex metadata). Special attention is paid to **scientific workflows**, or “workflow-centric research object”³⁸ and their reproducibility.

In 2019, K. Fenlon published an interesting contribution on applying the RO within the humanities domain. The challenges are many, e.g.:

[...] humanities ROs will require documenting provenance at a level of nuance that may exceed the capacity of automated or systematic capture; humanities scholarship requires “thick,” multilayered, context-rich provenance descriptions to accommodate conflicting assertions and formalize the expression of uncertainty. (Fenlon 2019, p. 510)

Regarding workflows, Fenlon quotes a study by T. Blanke and M. Hedges (2013) showing that humanities scholars employ sequential ones but that there is “scant evidence of usefully reproducible workflows”.

³⁶ For more recent developments on the FAIR Digital Object see the FAIR Digital Objects Forum at <https://fairdo.org>. They have a steering committee, that includes some of the people involved in the writing of the report, and different working groups.

³⁷ Work on ROs is led by [researchobject.org](https://www.researchobject.org/), a consortium maintained by the eScience Lab at the University of Manchester. See <https://www.researchobject.org/>

³⁸ For more on this, see also Belhajjame, Zhao, et al. (2015).

Our interviews with researchers at FICLIT led us to a partially different conclusion: some disciplines within the humanities, even very “traditional” ones such as philology, have **extremely specific and reproducible workflows**. The problem seems to be at the level of the expression and formalisation of these workflows, which tend to be implicit, and passed on from teachers to students within universities (see [section 5.4.2](#)).

Please note that throughout our interviews we have not employed the term “workflow”³⁹ but rather the more general term “methodology”⁴⁰. While workflows often have a specific connotation, as something extremely systematic and streamlined, we consider it equivalent to methodology in this context.

Fenlon concludes by pointing out that (bold is mine):

While autogenerated, computer-useable workflows may not apply to most humanities research processes, **formalized, (semi-) manually captured workflows would be highly useful for review, validation, archiving, reproducibility, reuse, and other purposes**. While the RO model has the capacity and flexibility for complex workflow representation, more research is needed to characterize humanities workflows; to identify how such characterizations can be made useful; and to identify model extensions and unique implementation strategies workflows might require in different domains. (Fenlon 2019, p. 512)

2.5 Peculiar challenges for FAIR in the arts and humanities

2.5.1 The “thick description”⁴¹

As we have seen in the introduction, E. Tóth-Czifra (2019, p. 3) points out that FAIR principles “have been implicitly designed according to underlying assumptions about how knowledge creation operates and communicates”. These underlying assumptions are: that scholarly data or metadata is digital by nature, that scholarly data is always created and therefore owned by researchers, and that there is “a wide community-level agreement on what can be considered as scholarly data” (*ibidem*).

None of this is true for the humanities for 3 main reasons. (i) Most scholarly data and metadata are held in galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAMs) and only a fraction of them has been digitised:

only one third (34%) of the digitised cultural heritage resources are currently available online, with barely 3% of these works is suitable for real creative reuse, meaning, only this 3% has the chance to fulfil the discipline-specific measures of being FAIR. (Tóth Czifra 2019, p. 5)

³⁹ “Flusso di lavoro” in Italian.

⁴⁰ “Metodologia” in Italian.

⁴¹ Borrowed from cultural anthropology, “thick description” is “a way of providing cultural context and meaning that people place on actions, words, things, etc. [...] so that a person outside the culture can make meaning of the behaviour” (Tóth Czifra 2019).

(ii) Data in the humanities are represented, not created. This brings peculiar challenges, such as the many “legal and ethical restrictions in which use conditions of cultural heritage sources are embedded”. Even when such restrictions do not exist, the complexities and uncertainties of interpreting the legal status of these data, which “are not only representations of history but also come themselves with a history”, are the real obstacle. Unfortunately, these legal barriers can sometimes apply to metadata, too (*ibidem*, p. 4).

Another important point is that digitising cultural heritage risks separating data from the curators, losing information and “providing [...] a thusly impoverished form of online access to such remediated knowledge” and “simulacra that are misleading in their apparent completeness”. **Humanities data need “complexity and context” in order to fulfil the FAIR principles of reusability and interoperability.** At the same time, the uneven distribution of funds to devote to digitisation projects between research institutions risks leading us to a partial and skewed view of our cultural heritage (*ibidem*, p. 11).

As the author puts it,

The creation of digital objects for arts and humanities research purposes is [...] not an innocent practice: it’s not merely a prerequisite for digitally-enabled research but is an important scholarly activity in itself. (*ibidem*, p. 13)

The humanities thus represent a “scholarly data continuum” where is not easy to separate knowledge representation from knowledge creation.

(iii) Pointing out that data is still a problematic concept in the humanities, the author calls for:

Iterated and large-scale surveys [...] to assess whether and to what extent the term data is still a dirty word in the increasingly digital humanities disciplines and how the evolving landscape of Open data and FAIR data policies impact and transform such conceptions of data. (*ibidem*, p. 15)

Only a small community of researchers is currently involved in data sharing and curation. For lack of incentives, on the one hand, and for “the lack of social life of data”, on the other: only the creation of a social community around repositories (e.g., through data peer review) can keep them alive and, perhaps, eventually change the mechanisms of research evaluation (Tóth Czifra 2019).

In summary, and I quote:

1. Data-drivenness is not yet a mature concept in arts and humanities. Consequently, there is a need for consolidated interpretative frameworks aimed at helping to reach consensus about what can be considered as research data and what is not [...].
2. Data in arts and humanities are rather collected than generated.
3. Data in arts and humanities show a highly networked but also highly scattered picture (continuum).
4. [...] the risk of losing contextual information around research sources that are essential for their productive reuse in the course of remediation of scholarly data is more than high [...].

5. [...] Aligning the slowly emerging scholarly practice of data sharing with the inadequately ageing institutions of book and article publishing is a key step towards a more open, more connected, more transparent and more sustainable research ecosystem. (*ibidem*, pp. 22-24)

While it is impossible not to agree with most of these observations, 2 main objections can in our view be raised.

On the one hand, the idea that data in the humanities are represented and not created is misleading. In the interviews that we carried out as part of this project, we asked researchers, all of them humanities scholars⁴², to describe the research materials they work with. This gave us a **list of 16 different materials all of which can, at least in principle, be both collected and generated**. According to our categorisation, the only type of data that cannot be created *ex-novo* is ancient manuscripts and early printed books – and even these have been generated at some point in the past, they simply cannot be created today (see [section 5.2](#)).

The peculiarity of the humanities, in our view, is not that data is only or mostly collected, but that in many cases a long time has passed from their generation. Humanists often work with objects that have crystallised in the past, while STEM practitioners usually work on phenomena of the immediate past, that they have observed directly⁴³. Of course, most social scientists and linguists are closer to the hard sciences in this respect, making the statement that data in the humanities are “rather collected than generated”, at the very least, limiting.

As we have discussed previously (see [section 2.3.1](#)), we also find the contraposition between the “emerging scholarly practice of data sharing” and “book and article publishing” difficult to sustain. While it is clear where this distinction originates, we argue that books and articles, indeed all types of scholarly publications, should be considered data in the FAIR framework.

2.5.2 “Provenance, value, importance, and authority”

Another extremely interesting analysis can be found in J. Edmond’s work. Her chapter *Power, Practices, and the Gatekeepers of Humanistic Research in the Digital Age* presents the results of a 2013 NeDiMAH network⁴⁴ meeting, convened to identify some of the major challenges facing humanities scholars. One of these is “the need to differentiate between two divergent processes: communication and publication”, whose relationship is “increasingly muddy”.

- **communication**: making data and results public,

⁴² For a list of the disciplines covered, see [section 3.2](#).

⁴³ This echoes the distinction between primary and secondary data we also find in the ALLEA report (Harrower, Maryl et al. 2020).

⁴⁴ <https://www.dariah.eu/activities/projects-and-affiliations/nedimah/>

- **publication**: submitting them to peer review or other sort of verification by the scholarly community (may or may not include the publisher editing, enriching, and enhancing the work) (Edmond 2019, p. 4).

In wondering what humanities research data are, Edmond asks:

should this term be understood to encompass all inputs, outputs, and intermediary products related to our processes; or only those digital, quantifiable, relatively tidy streams and collections that are readily processed, federated, and aggregated? (*ibidem*, p. 6)

The opinions emerged in our interviews at FICLIT indeed showed that **most researchers (11/19) agreed with the first of these positions, while only a minority (5/19) defined them as circumscribed and quantifiable**⁴⁵.

In describing how “many humanists resist the term ‘data’ as a descriptor for their primary and secondary sources, or indeed for almost anything they produce in the course of their research” Edmond indicates some of the possible reasons (the bold is mine):

The fact that humanists already have a much **richer and more nuanced vocabulary** to describe these research objects is surely a part of the reason for this resistance, but **the manner in which the term ‘data’ is deployed in disciplines that are primarily data-driven may also be a part of the hesitation** concerning its adoption. (Edmond 2019, p. 6)

The term “data”, Edmond argues, is too vague and applies to “inputs, results, or intermediary research outputs”.

The differentiation in provenance, value, importance, and authority of these different types of objects is one that humanists are highly sensitive to, making the adoption of the word ‘data’, with all of its slippery overdetermination, problematic indeed. (*ibidem*, p. 6)

This point did emerge from the interviews we carried out at FICLIT, but perhaps not as strongly as we would have expected: **3 researchers** (of the total 19) **expressed unease with the term “data”, with only 1 of them objecting strongly to its use as too generic, useless, and reductive** (see [section 5.9](#)).

Edmond also discusses issues around evaluation (which is currently based on impact, rather than excellence), trust in digital technologies, fragmentation of the humanities landscape and new forms of collaboration. One interesting remark is that “the blanket term of ‘the humanities’” puts together fields that are very diverse “in terms of methodologies, in terms of expectations, and in terms of the availability and nature of sources [...]” (*ibidem*, p. 8).

The “new objects” of the digital age have made old forms of evaluation obsolete. In Edmond’s view,

⁴⁵ Interestingly, this second definition comes mostly from researchers belonging to the field of language and linguistics. For our division of interviewees in disciplinary areas see [section 3.2](#).

[...] a part of the solution must lie in an enhanced need for **explicit methodologies, which are documented and, therefore verifiable**. (*ibidem*, p. 15, bold is mine)

This, however, is not going to happen easily, as

[...] it is the nature of the humanities scholar to build his or her **personalised epistemic instrument on the basis of a long process of curating and assimilating resources and influences**. This fact, which makes it difficult to step into the process of another scholar, or even to reuse of their data, is something we struggle to adapt to. (*ibidem*, pp. 15-16)

This is certainly part of the way humanities research works but, when we asked researchers at FICLIT whether they have a precise methodology, recognised across the field, the vast majority immediately replied “yes”. **Even among philologists and literary critics**, which we could argue are more “traditional” than researchers working in, e.g., linguistics or archival and library studies, **a staggering 11 out of 12 researchers claimed they have a precise methodology**. The situation is more nuanced as far as the description and formalisation of these methods is concerned: some interviewees commented that the methodology is formalised in manuals, as well as in preceding critical works that have become “milestones”. This is certainly a long way away from “explicit [...] documented and, therefore verifiable” methodologies (Edmond 2019, p. 15), but it seems to suggest that the field is mature for this kind of discussion (see [section 5.4.2](#)).

Finally, Edmond presents a taxonomy of scholarly outputs, also emerging from the NeDiMAH meeting, that we are going to mention again in the discussion (see [section 5.2](#)). Note that, of the six categories below, “only one [...] has a clear precedent and place in the traditional flows of production, dissemination, and evaluation, namely print paradigm publications within closed formats” (Edmond 2019).

The categories are:

- **print paradigm publications** within closed formats (such as PDF documents),
- **electronic paradigm publications**, “a broad category that included everything from enhanced publications to blogs and Twitter corpora, to arguments presented in video and audio”,
- **single or collected/curated primary sources**,
- **software**,
- **patents/licenses** (later discarded as more of a validation mechanism for other outputs),
- **ephemera**, such as exhibitions and performances (also found ineligible to stand as a category in its own right at a later date, since they “necessarily require some documentation”) (Edmond 2019, pp. 2-3).

2.6 Asking researchers: studies on data management practices

In this section we look at previous studies on the definition of data and on data management practices of university staff at different levels, across different disciplines and in different countries.

2.6.1 Online survey at Emory University (Atlanta), 2013

The article describing this study begins by defining research data as anything “underlying” publications:

Research data need not merely serve as material underlying conference papers, journal articles, and books. Rather, if documented, preserved and made accessible, datasets can stand alone as scholarly products. (Akers and Doty, 2013, p. 6)

However, in the conclusions, they state they have found that:

arts and humanities researchers (as well as librarians) may benefit from participating in conversations about definitions of arts and humanities research data and how they may differ from those for other research domains. (*ibidem*, p. 17)

They conducted an online survey consisting of 10 questions, aimed at all employees of Emory University with faculty status, with the primary objective of gathering “information on researchers’ practices and perspectives to guide development of library services to support the management of research data” (*ibidem*, p. 16).

The first question read: “Do you conduct research that generates some type of data (e.g., spreadsheets, text, images, videos, audio files, instrument files, photographs, physical samples/specimens, etc.)?”, while the following 9 enquired about current storage and back-up methods, use of data management plans (DMPs), data sharing practices, use of repositories and documentation. To conclude, they asked researchers what services they would use if offered by their university (*ibidem*, pp. 22-26).

For the analysis, they divided faculty members into four broad research domains: “the arts and humanities, social sciences, medical sciences, and basic sciences”⁴⁶ (*ibidem*, p. 7). They performed a statistical analysis, calculating the sample representativeness using Z-tests and evaluating the differences in responses among the different fields using chi-square tests (*ibidem*, p. 7).

The results were found to be “largely consistent with this existing body of information”. In particular:

⁴⁶ “Arts and humanities respondents were faculty members in area studies, art history, classics, creative writing, history, languages, liberal arts, literature, music, philosophy, religion, theater studies and theology” (*ibidem*, p. 7).

- arts and humanities researchers are more likely to state that they do not know how much data they are storing and to be completely unfamiliar with funding agency requirements for DMPs;
- most faculty researchers do not share their research data outside of their research group and arts and humanities researchers are least willing to do so (the main reasons being: personal and/or sensitive information in the data, fear of not getting credit for their data, data might be misinterpreted or misused). However, they are more willing to share their data with the general public;
- most researchers do not use repositories to deposit their data;
- most researchers are unfamiliar with documenting and/or creating metadata;
- they are interested in attending workshops on data management practices and in receiving assistance with DMPs (*ibidem*, pp. 8-14).

The results of our interviews at FICLIT, confirm, exclusively for the arts and humanities⁴⁷, some of these conclusions. In particular: only 2 out of 19 researchers mentioned using services for data storage and preservation different from Dropbox or Google Drive (see [section 5.7](#)), while documentation and metadata are familiar only to a small subset of our interviewees (4/19) (see [section 5.4.1](#)).

As for the willingness to share research data with colleagues, our results differ: **we found collaboration to be extremely important for our interviewees, both in the form of informal sharing to collect opinions and feedback (9/19) and in the form of teamwork (12/19)** (see [section 5.5.1](#)).

2.6.2 Online survey at the University of Minnesota Twin Cities, 2015

This survey was initially designed for the College of Liberal Arts and later adapted and used in other major campuses. The main objective was “understanding differences in user needs across and within academic colleges” to inform service development, outreach and education (Hofelich Mohr et al. 2015, p. 52).

The authors start from the assumption that:

not all researchers see the materials they work with as “data,” and, more importantly, not all agree with the notion that those materials even should be considered data. (*ibidem*, p. 51)

As such, the survey was designed to allow researchers to select between 2 sets of questions, containing **alternatively the word “data”, or the expression “research materials”**. They found that:

⁴⁷ Please note that our analysis is confined to researchers working within the Classical Philology and Italian Studies department at the University of Bologna (see [section 3.2](#)).

a significant portion of survey respondents chose not to describe their work as “data,” suggesting that an intentionally flexible approach to the language of research can broaden the reach of this kind of needs assessment. (*ibidem*, p. 51)

Within the College of Liberal Arts, **54% of the respondents said they worked with data, and 46% preferred the expression research materials** (*ibidem*, p. 52).

In our own interviews, we avoided the term “data” until the penultimate question and used the expression “research materials” instead (see also [section 3.1](#)). However, we found that the term “data” was not particularly problematic for our interviewees, with 14 (of the total 19) responding that they indeed work with data. All in all, only 3 researchers expressed unease with the term, with 1 of them strongly objecting to its use. Perhaps surprisingly, 12 researchers unwittingly used the term in connection with their work before it was first introduced by us (see [section 5.8](#)).

The survey questions by Hofelich Mohr and colleagues, which are available for download on the University of Minnesota's Digital Conservancy⁴⁸, revolve around:

- types of materials/data that researchers produce,
- if and how they store and back-up them,
- if and how materials/data are shared,
- which materials/data are kept or discarded,
- familiarity with and use of DMPs,
- kind of support needed from the university.

The main takeaway of their analysis is that researchers working with data want support with long term data preservation and with sharing, while those working with “research materials” have slightly different needs, although “help with long term preservation and better access to resources to support data management were common themes” (Hofelich Mohr et al. 2015, p. 51)

They conclude that their survey

[...] has been successful in reaching researchers that may not be comfortable describing their scholarly and academic work as “data” – those who may see the term as a dirty word rather than the basis of their research. We invite others to test our survey tool at their campus. (*ibidem*, p. 52)

2.6.3 Retrospective study at the University of Lille, 2015

Between 2014 and 2015, Prost, Malleret and Schöpfel conducted a survey on about 300 print and electronic dissertations in SSH submitted to the University of Lille 3 (France) between 1987 and 2013 (Prost, Malleret and Schöpfel 2015, p. 1).

⁴⁸ <http://hdl.handle.net/11299/174051>

They focused on the presence, or absence, of research data appended to them, and on the source, type, size and mode of publishing of these data (*ibidem*, p. 6). The main objectives were to help academic libraries in supporting PhD students with research data management and deposit, to curate research data and to develop content mining tools for their further exploitation (*ibidem*, p. 2).

These data, defined as re-usable research results, collected, observed, or created for purposes of analysis to produce original research results, are part of what is called “small data,” produced in a large variety of formats, sources, and types. Research results may be presented as tables, graphs, etc. in the paper or as additional material (appendix). (*ibidem*, p. 3)

They found that **66% of the dissertations were accompanied by data**. They opted for “**a large and pragmatic definition**” of the term, noting that:

This may not be completely satisfying but allows for a realistic study of submitted materials and data. (*ibidem*, p. 7)⁴⁹

Their analysis found these “data types”:

- text samples (the most important data type),
- tables (spreadsheets),
- images (including drawings and posters),
- maps,
- photographs,
- statistics,
- graphs (including figures, charts and visualisations),
- databases,
- timelines (chronologies),
- audio-visual media (interviews) (*ibidem*, pp. 12-14).

Text samples, images, tables/graphs, and figures were found across all disciplines, while other data types were specific to one or two. They did not find a significant difference between print and electronic dissertations, concluding that “differences are more related to disciplinary methodologies than to support” (*ibidem*, p. 14).

Lamenting the methodological problem connected to the “difficult distinction between data sources and data types and, more generally, the definition of what research data is and what it is not” they list the following “three barriers to open data” (italic in the original):

- *Incomplete, inadequate or missing description of the whole datasets and/or individual data.* [...]
- *Missing organisation.* [...] a kind of information mash-up not suitable for further research.

⁴⁹ In a later contribution, Schöpfel, Kergosien and Prost propose to pragmatically distinguish between data used by researchers for their research and the data produced as a result of research: “Nos propres études sur le campus de l’Université de Lille 3 confirment une typologie propre aux sciences humaines et sociales mais illustrent surtout l’intérêt d’une distinction entre données primaires (sources) et secondaires (résultats), avec une classification différente” (Schöpfel, Kergosien and Prost 2017). Interestingly, we have also independently adopted this same distinction in our analysis (see [section 5.2](#)).

- *Inadequate format.* [...] data and text are glued together in a PDF file instead of being separated and published in adequate file formats [...] (*ibidem*, p. 15).

In our own project, we also compiled a list of research materials⁵⁰ – based on the answers to our interview questions – which in our opinion constitute the data humanities researchers work with. Unfortunately, our list and the one compiled by Prost, Malleret and Schöpfel are difficult to compare, as we did not consider “data types” but loosely categorised data according to their function within the research process. So, for example, we have a category called “digital representation of cultural objects” instead of having three separate categories for photographs, 3D models, and videos (seen [section 5.2](#)).

2.6.4 Interviews with humanities faculty at “a four-year university”, 2018

The study by J.L. Thoegersen is extremely close to ours in terms of methodology: it is based on interviews that the author conducted in 2016, the sample was selected from faculty directories, interviewees were invited to participate via e-mail and the interviews were recorded and then transcribed (Thoegersen 2018, pp. 493-94).

Unlike our own experience, however, interviewees belonged to the humanities faculty at large, the sample was selected randomly, and those who agreed to participate (9 in total) belonged to the following disciplines: history (2), English (4), languages (1), and philosophy (2) (*ibidem*, pp. 493-94).

After discovering this study, we decided to re-use Thoegersen’s questions⁵¹ with a few minor adjustments. Indeed:

- the use of the expression “research materials” throughout, with the 2 final questions introducing the term “data”, is particularly useful;
- asking researchers to describe one of their own projects is a clever icebreaker, and a good way to anchor the questions that follow to their experiences.

Our interviews, however, were conducted in Italian, which is the mother tongue of everybody involved. In [section 3.1](#) we have included a table that lists Thoegersen’s original questions and our own, with additions and modifications highlighted in italic.

While we used the Grounded Theory method (GTM) to analyse the answers received, Thoegersen employed the iterative approach described by G. Guest, K.M. MacQueen, and E.E. Namey⁵². The answers were analysed to gather information on the following aspects:

- storage and backup,

⁵⁰ For more on the choice of this expression, see above and [section 3.1](#)

⁵¹ The questions are published in Appendix to the article (Thoegersen 2018, p. 503).

⁵² Greg Guest, Kathleen M. MacQueen, and Emily E. Namey. (2012) *Applied Thematic Analysis*. Los Angeles: Sage, pp. 65-72.

- organization of materials/data,
- their protection,
- sharing,
- keeping (and discarding) materials/data,
- attitudes around data.

Most findings regarding data management practices coincide with ours. Interestingly, the evaluation and categorisation of the research materials interviewees reported working with, which was perhaps the most important aspect for us (see sections [5.2](#) and [5.3](#)), is not touched upon in Thoegersen’s analysis (*ibidem*, pp. 495-501).

Regarding conceptions of data, **the results reported by the author are in line with what emerged from our interviews**: most participants (6/9) “stated, with varying levels of confidence, that they would consider most of the research materials discussed to be data”, while 2 disagreed (*ibidem*, pp. 48-50). In our cohort, 13/19 took the former position and 2 the latter (the remaining 4 did not answer, see [sections 5.8](#)).

2.6.5 Discipline-specific interviews with the DARIAH-EU working group on RDM

DARIAH-EU, the Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities has recently launched a Research Data Management Working Group⁵³ with the specific aim to ground data management in everyday research practices in the arts and humanities, by involving researchers from all major disciplinary clusters, along with cultural heritage professionals and data management experts (DARIAH-EU 2022).

Researchers are invited to share their current data workflows, within a concrete project, together with their reflections. A Zotero group⁵⁴ has also been set up as part of the initiative, to work as a knowledge base of data management best practices in the humanities (DARIAH-EU 2022).

The first publication in this sense revolves around corpus linguistics and includes “a step-by-step description of a research data workflow involving the annotation of multilingual parliamentary corpora (French, German, British) according to the guidelines of the Text Encoding Initiative”. The 15-page document wants to “open the black box of data curation” through a very specific example and “provide inspiration to fellow scholars who are working within the same discipline and/or data type” (Tóth-Czifra and Truan 2021, p. 2):

[It] is *not* to be read as a best practice in the sense of ‘these are the solutions you need to follow under any circumstances’, but rather as a concrete application of how to implement reflections on Open Science when gathering and collecting your data, no matter for which purpose and where you come from (*ibidem*; italic and bold in the original).

⁵³ <https://www.dariah.eu/activities/working-groups/research-data-management/>

⁵⁴ https://www.zotero.org/groups/2427138/data_management_best_practices_in_the_humanities

Although this initiative, organised around the in-depth analysis of specific case studies, is certainly very different from the department-wide interviews that characterise our experience, the rationale is, we think, very similar. If we want to have any fruitful discussions around applying FAIR data principles to the art and humanities domain, we need to start looking at how researchers work day-to-day, “going as deep as possible in research practices” and linking the definition of data “to the workflow of knowledge creation” (CO-OPERAS & Giglia 2020², p. 1).

As mentioned earlier, we found that the vast majority of researchers in our cohort, even philologists and literary critics, claim to have a well-defined methodology. Their precise description and formalisation are a long way away, but humanists seem to be ready for this discussion (see [section 5.4.2](#)).

3. Methods and materials

This section is devoted to a description of the methodologies used to interview researchers at the Classical Philology and Italian Studies department (FICLIT) of the University of Bologna and to collect and analyse the answers received.

3.1 Interview questions

Before approaching researchers, we analysed a series of studies involving the staff of different universities, at various levels and across different disciplines, to establish what would be the best methodology to follow (see the previous [section 2.6](#)). The experience described by J.L. Thoegersen (2018) is particularly fitting because:

- the research relied on in-depth interviews to explore humanities faculty's conceptions of data and data management practices,
- researchers were selected from the faculty directory and were invited to be interviewed for this study via e-mail,
- interviews were recorded, and the recordings were then transcribed.

The most interesting aspect, in our opinion, consisted in how the interview was structured:

- it began by enquiring on the faculty members' **current research projects**,
- it then proceeded to ask which **research materials** interviewees collect, generate, and use in their research, and how they manage them,
- it introduced the term "**data**" only at the very end, asking whether interviewees considered this term applicable to their own research.

From early on, we had feared that using the term "data" might alienate at least a part of our interviewees and we found the expression "research materials" –used by both Hofelich Mohr and colleagues (2015) and by Thoegersen (2018) – to be an excellent solution.

Also, beginning the conversation by asking each interviewee to describe their own research project would be, in our estimation, a very good way to establish a rapport and make sure that the following questions would be better understood and anchored in each interviewee individual experience.

A central difference is that our interviews were conducted in Italian, which is the mother tongue of everybody involved in the project. The word "data" was translated as "dati" but the expression "open data", mentioned in one of the final questions, was left unchanged since it is usually never translated. The table below lists Thoegersen's questions in the left-hand column and our own questions, in Italian, in the right-hand one. The additions we made are highlighted in *italic*.

Table 3.1: Interview questions, original and modified by us

N	Original questions (Thoegersen 2018)	Our questions (<i>additions in italics</i>)
1	To get started, can you describe your current research for me? (Guiding: Could you tell me more about that? What do you mean by that? Could you give me an example? Could you go into a little more detail? Could you tell me how that looks in the class? Can you explain that in a different way? Could you explain that further?)	Per cominciare, mi descriverebbe brevemente i/il progetti/o di ricerca che sta portando avanti in questo periodo?
2	I would like you to create a complete a list as possible of the materials you used in your research. Please write down any materials you have generated or collected in the course of this research. (Guiding: What other materials do you generate? Are there any other materials that you collect?)	Vorrei creare una lista il più possibile completa dei materiali di ricerca normalmente utilizzati nella sua disciplina (<i>sto pensando ad es. a fonti primarie, oppure pubblicazioni, ma anche o qualsiasi altro tipo di materiale, inteso nel modo più ampio possibile</i>). Mi può elencare il tipo di materiali che sta raccogliendo e/o creando nella sua ricerca?
3	Can you describe each of these materials for me? (Guiding: Where do you store the material? Do you keep any documentation on the material? Are there file formats that you use frequently? Are there any standards followed in your discipline for the material? Do you keep backups of these materials?)	a. Mi potrebbe descrivere ciascuno di questi materiali? <i>In particolare, vorrei saperne di più del loro formato, analogico o digitale che sia, e come/dove sono conservati.</i> b. <i>E sono solitamente accompagnati da qualche tipo di documentazione? Ci sono degli standard riconosciuti all'interno della disciplina riguardo questi materiali?</i> c. <i>E sempre parlando di standard e di buone pratiche, esistono delle metodologie riconosciute e applicate di frequente all'interno della disciplina? Sono descritte o formalizzate in qualche modo?</i>
4	Can you describe who has access to these materials? Under what circumstances might you share these materials with other researchers? With the public? (Guiding: Which materials would you share? Can you provide an example of sharing research materials?)	Chi ha accesso a questi materiali? Li condivide (o li condividerebbe) con altri colleghi/ricercatori? E con il pubblico in generale (<i>per esempio online, ma non solo</i>)? (Altre indicazioni: Quali materiali condividerebbe con altri? Può farmi un esempio di condivisione dei materiali di ricerca?)
5	Of the materials you have listed, are there any that contain confidential information? Are there any that have privacy concerns? Intellectual property concerns? Security concerns? (Guiding: How do you handle this material? Do you have provisions for sharing this material?)	Qualcuno dei materiali elencati contiene informazioni confidenziali o che riguardano la privacy di qualcuno? Ci sono considerazioni da fare riguardo la loro proprietà intellettuale/copyright? E preoccupazioni riguardo la sicurezza <i>di qualcuno o qualcosa</i> ? (Altre indicazioni: Come gestisce questo tipo di materiale? Ci sono misure condivise per la gestione di questo materiale?)
6	How do you decide what research materials to keep or discard at the end of a research project? For those you keep, where do you keep them? (Guiding: Could you tell me more about that? What do you mean by that? Could you give me an example? Could you go into a little more detail?)	Come decide quali materiali conservare e quali scartare alla fine del progetto? E dove tiene quelli che decide di conservare? (Altre indicazioni: Mi può dire di più? Mi può fare un esempio? Può darmi qualche dettaglio in più?)
7	Think of the materials you generate and collect in the course of your research. Which, if any, of these would you consider data? (Guiding: What makes you consider this material to be data? What do you mean by that? Could you give me an example? Could you go into a little more detail?)	<i>Ultimamente si parla molti di "open data" e quindi di "dati" della ricerca. Ripensando ai materiali di cui abbiamo parlato, ce ne sono alcuni che considererebbe "dati"? Se sì, quali?</i> (Altre indicazioni: Cosa le fa dire che si tratta di dati? Cosa intende? Mi può fare un esempio? Può darmi qualche dettaglio in più?)

8	Could you describe or tell me what you mean by “data”? (Guiding: Could you give me an example? Could you go into a little more detail? Why do you approach data in this way?)	Più in generale, cosa mi risponderebbe se le chiedessi di definire la parola “dati”? (Altre indicazioni: Mi può fare un esempio? Può darmi qualche dettaglio in più? Perché definisce i dati in questo modo?)
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There are 3 changes worth discussing:

1. Question 2 reads, in translation: “I would like to create a complete a list as possible of the materials you used in your research. (*I am thinking about, e.g., primary sources, or publications, or any other type of materials, in the broadest possible sense of the word*). Please list any materials you have generated or collected in the course of this research”. Compared with the original, examples have been added in brackets. It could be argued that this addition is leading, but we felt that the word “materials” had to be explained, to avoid researchers feeling frustrated by a language unfamiliar and vague, or disengaging from the conversation.
2. Question 3 has been expanded because we felt that points raised in Thoegersen’s guiding questions (and especially “Do you keep any documentation on the material?” and “Are there any standards followed in your discipline for the material?”), deserved to be addressed in separate questions (3b and 3c). We also decided to address methodologies directly in question 3c, by asking: “*And since we are talking about standards and good practices, are there clearly recognised methodologies in your discipline? And are they described or formalised in any way?*”.
3. At the beginning of question 7, we decided to add a mention to open data: “*Lately there is a lot of talk about ‘open data’ and ‘research data’*. Think back at the materials we talked about; would you consider any of them ‘data’? If so, which ones?”. In our view, this would help researchers contextualise this complex question.

Please note that interviewees already knew that the project revolved around open data and open science, since it had briefly been mentioned in the e-mail invitations. Also, before beginning the interviews, I made a short introduction to this effect:

My thesis in Digital Humanities deals with open science in the humanities. [...] The objective is to better understand what we mean by research in the humanities. This is why I am going to ask some questions about your own research, with a particular focus on the materials and the methods you use.

I also asked participants not to discuss the topics of the interview with colleagues over the following weeks, to avoid influencing each other.

3.2 Selecting participants

Unlike Thoegersen, we contacted only researchers working within the Classical Philology and Italian Studies department (FICLIT)⁵⁵, and not within the faculty at large⁵⁶.

We used the official disciplinary areas published by the Italian Ministry for education⁵⁷ to select our sample: we contacted via e-mail 1 researcher for each of the 19 disciplinary areas represented within the department. They all answered positively, and we arranged interviews in person (with 3 researchers) or via MS Teams⁵⁸ (with 16) over 3 weeks, from the 9th of November to the 1st of December 2021.

While analysing the interviews, however, we adopted a simpler categorisation into **5 main research areas**, as detailed in the table below.

Table 3.2: Macro-disciplines and number of researchers in our cohort

Macro-discipline	N. of researchers
Philology and literary criticism (ancient, modern and contemporary)	12
Language and linguistics	4
History of art (modern)	1
Computer science	1
Archival and library studies	1

At the beginning of each interview, we asked for consent to record (for the purpose of transcribing) and to use the transcript of the answers in the study. We recorded all conversations in their entirety and subsequently transcribed and anonymised them, including editing out content that could be used to identify the interviewee. The recordings were destroyed as promised, once the transcriptions were done and double-checked. The interview extracts quoted throughout this dissertation have been translated by us, and the original text in Italian is available in footnote.

In February 2022, we re-contacted interviewees for explicit permission to make the anonymised transcriptions available for further reuse. We are currently collecting their written consent and we will make available the transcriptions, in the original Italian, and the GMT coding at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6123290> (please note, the link has been “reserved” on the Zenodo repository but, on the date this dissertation is submitted, does not yet link to the transcriptions).

⁵⁵ <https://ficlit.unibo.it/it>

⁵⁶ The School of Arts, Humanities, and Cultural Heritage at the University of Bologna includes 3 other departments: Cultural Heritage, Philosophy and Communication, and History and Cultures.

⁵⁷ For a list of the academic disciplines for Italian University research and teaching, with their English translation, see https://www.cun.it/uploads/storico/settori_scientifico_disciplinari_english.pdf

⁵⁸ The most widely adopted video-conference platform at the University of Bologna during the Covid pandemic.

3.3 Analysis of the interviews

Our primary objective was to answer these 3 research questions:

1. If we want to implement FAIR principles in our respective fields, how do we define the word “data” in the humanities? What research materials should be considered as data?
2. What do researchers think of the word “data”? Is it problematic for them?
3. More generally, what are the attitudes towards open data and open science?

Secondarily, we wanted to gather information on how researchers work, if and how they use digital technologies, the methodologies they follow during research, if any, possible copyright and privacy concerns, current preservation strategies used, and more.

We have adopted the Grounded Theory method (GTM) to carry out the in-depth analysis of the answers we received in the 19 interviews. We followed the approach to GMT formalised by Cathy Urquhart in her 2013 publication *Grounded Theory for Qualitative Research: A Practical Guide*. Citing Cresswell and Dey, Urquhart describes the key features of grounded theory as follows (Urquhart 2013):

1. The aim of grounded theory is to generate or discover a theory.
2. The researcher has to set aside theoretical ideas in order to let the substantive theory emerge.
3. Theory focuses on how individuals interact with the phenomena under study.
4. Theory asserts a plausible relationship between concepts and sets of concepts.
5. Theory is derived from data acquired from fieldwork interviews, observation and documents.
[...]
11. Data analysis proceeds from open coding (identifying categories, properties and dimensions) through selective coding (clustering around categories) to theoretical coding.
12. The resulting theory can be reported in a narrative framework or a set of propositions.

For open and selective coding, we used QualCoder⁵⁹ version 2.8, a qualitative data analysis application written in python3 and released under the permissive MIT license⁶⁰. It uses a SQLite database⁶¹ to store coding data (Curtain 2021).

⁵⁹ <https://github.com/ccbogel/QualCoder>

⁶⁰ <https://mit-license.org/>

⁶¹ <https://sqlite.org/index.html>

4. Results

By analysing the 19 transcribed interviews with the help of GTM we gathered a wealth of information on many different but related topics: attitudes towards and use of technology, methodologies used in research, copyright and privacy concerns, preservation strategies used, and so on. For a discussion of everything that emerged, please see [section 5](#).

Here, we will focus on the 3 main research questions we set out in the introduction:

1. How do we define “data” in the humanities? What research materials should be considered as data?
2. What do researchers think of the word “data”? Is it problematic for them?
3. More generally, what are the attitudes towards open data and open science?

4.1 Research question 1: How do we define “data” in the humanities? What research materials should be considered as data?

As mentioned in [section 3.1](#), we avoided using the term “data” in our interviews until the penultimate question, using “research materials” instead. Thanks to this expression we could enquire on **what sort of inputs and outputs researchers in our sample work with**, postponing any terminological or conceptual discussions to the later stages of the conversation. Please bear in mind that some interviewees talked about more than 1 project, and that each project used and produced a, sometimes high, number of different materials.

4.1.1 *What research materials do researchers produce?*

Table 4.1: Types of research materials produced

Type of research output	Produced by (tot. 19)
publications	18
events	6
digital representation of cultural objects	4
websites (ancillary)	4
digital infrastructures	3
documentation	3
corpora	2
software	2
personal data	2
databases	2
born-digital artifacts	1

Unsurprisingly, most researchers (18) report producing **traditional “print-paradigm”⁶² publications** and especially, in order of frequency, critical editions, journal articles, monographs or edited books, essays, and reading editions. They also organise **events**,

⁶² We have borrowed this term from Edmond (2019). See also [section 2.5.2](#).

consisting in conferences, exhibitions, webinars, guided tours and teacher trainings (6 researchers).

Digital representations of cultural objects, used by 4, include facsimiles and photographs, 3D models, and videos. Across our cohort, **websites** (4) are all informative and mostly textual, aimed exclusively at publicising the project; **digital infrastructures**, on the other hand, are built to allow interaction with users and consist of a mobile app, a 3D web viewer, and a collaborative platform (3). In the case of **databases** (2), the technical infrastructure had already been created, and the research activity consisted in populating them with relevant information (e.g., through cataloguing).

Other outputs are:

- **documentation** (3), consisting in deliverables for funders and project notes,
- **linguistic corpora** (2),
- **software** (2),
- **personal data**⁶³ (2),
- **born-digital artifacts**⁶⁴ (1).

4.1.2 What research materials do researchers use?

Table 4.2: Types of research materials used

Research input	Used by (tot. 19)
publications	15
ancient manuscripts or early printed books	9
catalogues, databases or other search tools	9
digital representation of cultural objects	8
unpublished materials (modern or contemporary)	4
monuments, artworks or unique artifacts	3
archival documents	3
software	2
standards	2
born-digital artifacts	1

“Print-paradigm” publications are again at the top of the list (15) since researchers read extensively on their topic of choice. This includes 2 cases where a published text – a novel or other literary text – is the primary source of the research, and 2 cases where the material consists mostly of photographs (but published in a volume).

Since most researchers in our sample work in philology and literary criticism, **ancient manuscripts** and **early printed books** are important materials (9), as are modern and

⁶³ We consider personal data produced, rather than used, because we are referring to their collection into a coherent whole for the purpose of a research project. For a definition of personal data see:

https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/what-personal-data_en

⁶⁴ These are the by-products of users’ online interaction with a digital infrastructure (see previous paragraph). They are, e.g., tags, associations, texts.

contemporary **unpublished material** such as drawings, notes and letters (4). Other primary sources are **archival documents** (3), and **monuments, artworks or unique artifacts** such as tablets or vases (3).

Many interviewees (9) report using **catalogues, databases and other search tools**⁶⁵ to locate these materials, which are usually held in conservation institutes and are consulted upon request. Researchers often view these resources in person, but they also make ample use of their **digital representations** (8).

Other inputs are:

- **software** (2) written by others,
- **standards**⁶⁶ (2),
- **born-digital artifacts**⁶⁷ (1).

4.1.3 Our conclusions

The table below summarises the research materials our interviewees work with. Some of these materials are only produced, while others are only used⁶⁸.

Table 4.3: Comparing materials produced and used

Research material	Produced by (tot. 19)	Used by (tot. 19)
publications	18	15
digital representation of cultural objects	4	8
catalogues, databases and other search tools	2	9
ancient manuscripts or early printed books	n/a	9
events	6	0
unpublished materials (modern or contemporary)	0	4
websites (ancillary)	4	0
software	2	2
documentation	3	0
digital infrastructures	3	0
archival documents	0	3
monuments, artworks or unique artifacts	0	2
personal data	2	0
corpora	2	0
standards	0	2
born-digital artifacts (tag, association, text)	1	1

⁶⁵ We realise this is an extremely broad category, including all the resources used to locate a primary source, find information about it, and sometimes access its digital representation. Examples include bibliographic and lexical databases, lexicons and dictionaries, catalogues; some contain digitised documents. Although this is certainly an over-simplification, we found a more detailed analysis to fall outside the scope of this project.

⁶⁶ Languages or other conventions officially recognised as the norm in a certain research field (e.g., for interoperability).

⁶⁷ The by-products of users' online activities we have seen earlier, which are used as input for further research.

⁶⁸ Ancient manuscripts and early printed books, by definition, cannot any longer be produced.

Whether we want to call them “data”, “materials”, or “resources”, these are the building blocks of research in the humanities, as emerged from the interviews. If we are looking to apply FAIR principles within the arts and humanities, and to ensure that these disciplines are represented within the EOSC, **these are the type of data we need to start reflecting on and developing infrastructures for.**

Publications emerge as the most important type of data in the humanities, both in terms of research output, but also in terms of input, be it primary or secondary sources (see [section 5.2](#)). So, at least in the humanities, **open access to scientific literature seems to be an integral part of open data policies.**

4.2 Research question 2: What do researchers think of the word “data”? Is it problematic for them?

4.2.1 *Are the materials we talked about “data”?*

When asked whether they would consider the research materials emerged during the interviews as data:

- **14 researchers responded positively.** Of these, however, **2 expressed a certain unease** with the term, and **1 objected** strongly to the use of the word “data”, as too generic, useless, and reductive;
- **2 researchers** answered they **do not deal with data**;
- **3 responded they did not know** the answer to this question.

Some **12 researchers** even **unwittingly used the term before it was first introduced by us** in question 7 and 8⁶⁹.

4.2.2 *How do researchers define data?*

Throughout the interviews, some researchers restricted the term “data” to something “circumscribed, objective and definable”, while others took a more inclusive view. Some seemed to go back and forth between these 2 positions. Considering each interviewee’s answers in full, we weighed the different statements they had made and rated their overall opinion on data on a scale from 5 (very generic, “everything is data”) to 1 (very precise, “data are circumscribed and objective”). The results are shown in the table below.

⁶⁹ Of them, 6 used it exclusively within the term “database” (“banca dati”), 2 referred to personal data (“dati personali”), 2 referred to gathering data as part of their research and another 2 used it several times and in different contexts.

Table 4.4: View on data on a scale from 5 (very generic) to 1 (very specific)

Rating	Definition of data	N. of researchers (tot. 19)
5	“everything is data”	2
4	very open, tends to include primary sources, interpretation, methodologies and research results	4
3	open, tends to include either one among primary sources, interpretation, methodologies, research results	5
2	somehow restrictive, but can include either primary sources, critical texts, and/or textual variants	2
1	restrictive: data is circumscribed and objective	3
n/a	no reply or could not confidently assign a rating	3

Overall, **most researchers included several, if not all, research materials in their definition of data** (11), while a **minority** (5) **defined them rather precisely** as “information items”, “raw materials”, or “quantitative components”. Interestingly, the most restrictive definitions all seem to come from researchers belonging to the field of language and linguistics⁷⁰.

It is worth noting that nobody, understandably, mentioned **interpretation and methodologies** when asked to list their research materials. However, by the end of the interview, **6 researchers had explicitly included them in their definition of research data**.

The reasons for this shift are unclear but it is reasonable to think that question 3c, which focused the interviewees attention on disciplinary-specific methodologies and their potential formalisation⁷¹, had something to do with it. We might also hypothesise that the mention of “open data” at the start of question 7⁷² prompted, in some cases, a comparison with the hard sciences and a desire to underline how methodologies play as much a role in the arts and humanities as in the hard sciences.

4.3 Research question 3: More generally, what are the attitudes towards open data and open science?

Some researchers within the group we have interviewed expressed concerns around:

- the use of article/book processing charges (APC/BPC) in open access publishing (1 researcher);
- the new rules around EU-funded projects, particularly the speed at which changes are being implemented and the imposition of open access for monographs, which limits researchers in their choice of a publisher for their work (3);

⁷⁰ For our division of the sample in macro-discipline see [section 3.2](#).

⁷¹ “And, speaking of standards and good practices, are there recognised, frequently applied methodologies in your discipline? And are they somehow described or formalised?”

⁷² “Lately there is a lot of talk about ‘open data’ and ‘research data’. Think back at the materials we talked about; would you consider any of them ‘data’? If so, which ones?”. See [section 3.1](#) for the full list of questions.

- the difficulty of more traditional, less methodologically innovative, research projects in accessing funding in the current landscape (3).

Others reported a rather positive attitude, expressing:

- a willingness to share research data and a desire to “give back” to society the results of research (4);
- a desire for support from universities and public institutions, especially regarding research infrastructures, eliminating the need to rely on commercial third-party services (2);
- concerns about traditional publishers protecting academic works excessively and in fact preventing the circulation of research results (2);
- a desire to see primary sources digitised and made available for research (2).

Across all interviews, we counted 18 statements that we categorised as positive, and 10 that we categorised as negative. We can therefore conclude that **positive attitudes towards open data and open science are prevalent among the participants to our study.**

5. Discussion

We are now going to look in detail at the information we gathered from the 19 researchers we interviewed at the FICLIT department at the University of Bologna. We will take the interview questions one by one and describe the answers we received. The analysis, carried out with the help of GTM, did not strictly follow the structure of the interview, and in some cases considers statements made in other parts of the interviews, if considered relevant to the topic at hand.

We are going to quote some passages directly from the interviews, as we believe there is nothing quite as powerful as hearing the voices of researchers first-hand. However, these are not intended to cover everything that was said across the interviews about a certain topic. They are just excerpts, sentences that we found particularly interesting and that we felt would enrich the discussion. The English translation is ours, and the original text in Italian can be found in footnote.

This analysis has, of course, some limitations, namely the small sample of participants and the inclusion of only 5 disciplinary areas: philology and literary criticism, language and linguistics, history of art, computer science, archival and library studies. Ideally, it should be replicated on a larger sample, and should take into account other humanities disciplines, such as, e.g., history and philosophy.

5.1 The projects

In total, the interviews cover 21 projects, not 19, because 2 interviewees, both in philology and literary criticism⁷³ decided to talk about 2 different projects during their interview. We have included these “extra” projects in the analysis because we are interested in covering as many different cases as possible, the analysis is qualitative, and we do not make any comparisons on the number of projects by discipline.

Regarding the research project(s) to describe, we invited interviewees to choose something they considered representative of their field. Most of them described recently concluded projects, while 3 decided to talk about an ongoing project.

⁷³ For a description of how we categorised scholars into macro-disciplines, please see [section 3.2](#).

5.2 Types of material produced and used in research

I analyse here the main research inputs and outputs, as described by the interviewees when answering questions 1 and 2. We have already described how, at this stage, we used the term “research material” to avoid possible leading terms and, crucially, the term “data” (see [section 3.1](#)).

Question 2 asked: “I would like to create a complete a list as possible of the materials you used in your research. (I am thinking about, e.g., primary sources, or publications, or any other type of materials, in the broadest possible sense of the word). Please list any materials you have generated or collected in the course of this research”⁷⁴. As mentioned, the examples added in brackets may be considered leading, but we felt that the word “materials” had to be explained, to avoid researchers feeling frustrated by a language unfamiliar and vague, or disengaging from the conversation.

Please bear in mind that some interviewees talked about more than 1 project, and that each project used and produced a, sometimes high, number of different materials.

5.2.1 Materials produced

While open coding the interviews, we extracted all the materials that researchers reported producing as a result of their research projects. Of course, we cannot assume this list to be exhaustive: some input materials might have been forgotten, or not considered “materials” in the first place.

Table 5.1: Types of research materials produced

Type of research output	Produced by (tot. 19)
publications	18
events	6
digital representation of cultural objects	4
websites (ancillary)	4
digital infrastructures	3
documentation	3
corpora	2
software	2
personal data	2
databases	2
born-digital artifacts	1

Publications are by far the most mentioned material, with only 1 researcher describing a project that did not include a “traditional” publication among its outputs. The term “**print paradigm publications**” (Edmond 2019) should probably be preferred here, as some of these have a digital version in a closed format such as PDF. If we break down this broad

⁷⁴ To read the untranslated question in Italian, and how it compares to Thoegersen’s question, see [section 3.1](#).

category, we see that, across the 21 projects described by our interviewees, the following types of publication have been produced (in brackets you find the number of projects, the same project may have produced more than one type of publication):

- critical editions (8),
- journal articles (8),
- monographs or edited books (4),
- essays (3),
- reading editions (2).

Our interviewees are mostly philologists and literary critics, which explains why critical editions⁷⁵ are the most common type of publication, while monographs and edited books, generally considered the typical publication format in the humanities (Avanço et al., 2021; Crossick 2015), are as common as journal articles in our sample. We have not considered critical editions as monographs because, in our opinion, they are too different: the edition of a critically reconstructed text in one case, the discursive discussion of a research topic in the other. It is worth noting that no philologist in our group worked on digital scholarly editions.

Events are perhaps surprisingly high up in the list: 6 interviewees report having organised at least one event as part of their project. We have considered an event any one-off gathering of people organised as a result of a research project, to share ideas, offer training, or present something to the public. They are (in brackets you find the number of projects, the same project may have produced more than one type of events):

- conferences (4),
- exhibitions (2),
- webinars (2),
- guided tour (1),
- teacher training (1).

Interestingly, in the classification we mentioned in [section 2.5.2](#), Edmond had originally included a category called “Ephemera”⁷⁶. This category is well represented in this sample, and it is important to note that, in at least 2 cases, the event constitutes one of the main outputs of the project.

I have defined a **digital representation of a cultural object** the result of a process that aims at capturing the main characteristics of a certain physical object or cultural event and make it accessible in a digital environment. In this specific sample, it **includes facsimiles, photographs, 3D models, and videos**. Please note that only 2 of the 4 projects produced

⁷⁵ For an in-depth description of what a critical edition is, please go to [section 5.4.2](#).

⁷⁶ Which was later found to be ineligible to stand as a category in its own right, since it “necessarily requires some documentation” (Edmond 2019, p. 3).

digital representations of cultural objects with the explicit aim of making them widely available; in the other 2 cases, photos of the manuscripts were taken exclusively to help with their analysis and with the clear understanding they would never be made public⁷⁷. This category seems to be falling within what Edmond calls “single or collected/curated primary sources” (Edmond 2019, p. 2).

We have broken down Edmond’s extremely broad category “electronic paradigm publications” into at least 3 separate categories. On the one hand we have **websites**, mentioned by 4 interviewees, which in our sample are all informative, mostly textual, web resources making ample use of hyperlinks. Their aim is to document and/or publicise the research project, without being a central deliverable. They are often hosted on university servers, with the university branding. As for the other digital publications,

- 3 projects have produced what we have called a **digital infrastructure**, designed to allow complex online interactions – they are a **mobile app**, a **3D model web viewer**, and a **platform** respectively;
- 2 projects worked on online **databases**, cataloguing cultural objects and making information available to other researchers for the first time. Here, the technical infrastructure had already been created and was not part of the project.

The materials in the list above constitute the primary research output of their respective projects.

A digital infrastructure requires **software** to be written and then executed. Two researchers reported creating software as part of their research. We also find this category in Edmond (2019, p. 2).

Finally, we find some outputs that are not mentioned in Edmond’s classification:

- **documentation**, consisting in deliverables for funders (2) and project notes (1);
- **corpora** (2), a category specific to linguistics research: natural language is produced and recorded in a controlled, experimental, environment and then stored (mostly digitally) to allow further research on relevant linguistic phenomena;
- **personal data**: 2 projects handle personal data as an important part of their operations⁷⁸. These are always protected and never shared (see [section 5.6](#));
- what we called **born-digital artefacts** (1), created as a by-products of users’ online interaction with a digital infrastructure (see above). They are, e.g., tags, associations, texts.

⁷⁷ For more on this topic, please see [section 5.3](#).

⁷⁸ We consider personal data created, rather than used, because we are referring to the collection of personal data into a coherent whole for the purpose of a research project. For a definition of personal data see: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/what-personal-data_en

5.2.2 Materials used

We look here at the materials participants reported using in a recent research project. Bear in mind, again, that we cannot assume this list to be exhaustive.

Table 5.2: Types of research materials used

Research input	Used by (tot. 19)
publications	15
ancient manuscripts or early printed books	9
catalogues, databases or other search tools	9
digital representation of cultural objects	8
unpublished materials (modern or contemporary)	4
monuments, artworks or unique artifacts	3
archival documents	3
software	2
standards	2
born-digital artifacts	1

“**Print-paradigm**” **publications** are again at the top of the list (15) since researchers read extensively on their topic of choice. This includes 2 cases where a published text –a novel or other literary text – is the primary source of the research, and 2 cases where the material mostly consists of photographs (but published in a volume) rather than text.

Since most researchers in our sample work in philology and literary criticism, **ancient manuscripts** and **early printed books** are important materials (9), as are modern and contemporary **unpublished material** such as drawings, notes and letters (4). Other primary sources are **archival documents** (3), and **monuments, artworks and artifacts** such as tablets or vases (3).

Many interviewees (9) report using **catalogues, database and other search tools** to locate these materials⁷⁹, which are usually held in conservation institutes and are consulted upon request. Researchers often view these resources in person, but they also make ample use of their **digital representations** (8). See [section 5.3](#) for a discussion of the attitudes towards facsimiles and digitisation among interviewees.

We saw that **software** was produced as part of 2 projects, which both built on pre-existing software that was available under open licenses. Two researchers report using **standards**, defined here as languages or other conventions officially recognised as the norm in a certain research field (e.g., for interoperability). Finally, **born-digital artifacts**, or the by-products of users’ online activities (see above), were used as input for further research in 1 project.

⁷⁹ We realise this is an extremely broad category, including all those resources that researchers use to locate a primary source, find information about it, and sometimes access its digital representation. Examples include bibliographic and lexical databases, lexicons and dictionaries, catalogues; some contain digitised documents (Internet Archive, Google Books). Although this is certainly an over-simplification, we found any more detailed analysis to fall outside the scope of this project.

5.2.3 Putting it all together

The table below summarises the **16 research materials our interviewees work with**. In this specific instance, some of these materials are only produced, while others are only used⁸⁰.

Table 5.3: Comparing materials produced and used

Research material	Produced by (tot. 19)	Used by (tot. 19)
publications	18	15
digital representation of cultural objects	4	8
catalogues, databases or other search tools	2	9
ancient manuscripts or early printed books	n/a	9
events	6	0
unpublished materials (modern or contemporary)	0	4
websites (ancillary)	4	0
software	2	2
documentation	3	0
digital infrastructures	3	0
archival documents	0	3
monuments, artworks, or unique artifacts	0	2
personal data	2	0
corpora	2	0
standards	0	2
born-digital artifacts	1	1

Whether we want to call them “data”, “materials”, or “resources”, these are the building blocks of research in the humanities, as emerged from the interviews. If we are looking to apply FAIR principles within the arts and humanities, and to ensure that these disciplines are represented within the EOSC, **these are the type of data we need to start reflecting on and developing infrastructures for**.

Publications emerge as the most important type of data, in terms of research output, but also in terms of input (be it primary or secondary resources). So, at least in the humanities, **open access to scientific literature seems to be an integral part of open data policies**.

⁸⁰ Ancient manuscripts and early printed books, by definition, cannot any longer be produced.

5.3 The use of digital resources in the humanities

The third question revolved around the materials discussed previously, and centred on their format, whether physical or digital, and on their availability, online or otherwise. Question 3 is where we most diverged from the questions proposed by J. L. Thoegersen in her own interview. We felt that the original question (“Can you describe each of these materials for me?”) was too vague, and that it would be better to divide it into three separate questions, which we numbered 3a, 3b and 3c to keep the numbering of the following questions unchanged.

Here, we discuss the answers to question 3a, which asked: “Could you please describe each of these materials for me? I particularly would like to know more about their format, whether physical or digital, and how/where they are held”⁸¹ (for discussion around 3b and 3c see [section 5.4](#)).

Of course, some materials are inherently digital (digital representations of cultural objects, websites, digital infrastructures, software, born-digital artifacts), while others are inherently not (events, archival documents, manuscripts, early printed books, monuments, artworks and unique artifacts). However, this question allowed us to gauge how much research in the humanities has been permeated by the digital.

5.3.1 *Digital representation of cultural objects*

Perhaps the most interesting aspect that emerged at this stage was the **widespread use of digital representation of cultural objects, especially of manuscripts**. Five interviewees stated that digitisation of manuscripts or archive inventories radically changed the way of working with primary sources. In some cases, they allow access to otherwise inaccessible resources (e.g., due to geographical distance, geopolitical issues), in others they make it possible to better preserve the original documents, when they are too frail to be accessed and consulted with ease.

We know from [section 5.2.2](#) that 8 out of the total 19 participants claim to have used these digital representations in their research. Some interviewees however underlined their limits, stating that personal inspection of the documents is still required:

The digital is extraordinary because when the manuscript digitisation is well done, I can really see the details of the writing, [...] and this is extraordinary, but it is not enough⁸²

and that digital facsimiles available online can be of poor quality:

⁸¹ To read the untranslated question in Italian, and how it compares to Thoegersen’s question, see [section 3.1](#).

⁸² “[I]l digitale è straordinario perché quando la realizzazione di un manoscritto è fatta bene io posso vedere davvero la grana della scrittura, [...] questo è straordinario, ma non basta”.

In this instance, the reproduction is sub-optimal⁸³

Most of these digitisations do not have the level of quality that would be necessary⁸⁴.

Some researchers also described how they use photographs taken not by the holding institution, but rather by themselves or colleagues. One researcher mentioned a recent Italian law forcing public libraries to allow such pictures to be taken, exclusively for research purposes.

This last clause does not seem to be a massive issue for philologists or literary critics in our cohort, as they rarely include any images of the source documents within the final research output, which is often a critical edition. Two researchers commented specifically on this point, and one of them clarified they include facsimiles (or small portions of them) in monographs and articles on a more regular basis.

Things are quite different for the one art historian in our sample, who stated that digital images of artworks are fundamental for the discipline and should be freely available:

The problem of image copyright is a catastrophe because the cost of one single image can derail any budget. [...] A photograph can cost 200 €, and you can imagine [what happens] if one needs seven or eight of them⁸⁵.

As mentioned previously, only 2 projects made digital representations of cultural objects available to the public; in both cases, the publication of these materials online was one of the main deliverables of the project. In 1 case, the researcher had to negotiate with several institutions for access to the originals and for permission to digitise, admitting to a certain level of “competition” with the institutions.

These reflections were accompanied by comments on the state of the digitisation of our cultural heritage, with a particular focus on the work being done by libraries and archives. If 1 researcher complimented the digitisation campaigns undertaken by several important Italian libraries, many more defined the digitisation effort as slow and lacking:

In Italy manuscript digitisation is terribly behind, in the rest of Europe they are further down the line⁸⁶.

Digitisation of archival documents is rally behind [...]. After the start of the pandemic, many archives, especially State archives, have started digitising and publishing their inventories⁸⁷.

⁸³ “[N]ello specifico è una riproduzione non ottimale”.

⁸⁴ “[L]a maggior parte di queste digitalizzazioni non offrono le caratteristiche di qualità che invece sarebbe necessario avere”.

⁸⁵ “[I]l problema del copyright delle immagini per gli storici dell’arte rimane una catastrofe perché il costo di una singola immagine può far saltare qualsiasi budget. [...] Una foto può costare 200 € si può immaginare se uno ha bisogno di sette od otto foto”.

⁸⁶ “In Italia il processo di digitalizzazione dei manoscritti è a un livello di arretratezza terribile, mentre nel resto dell’Europa sono in fase più avanzata”.

⁸⁷ “La digitalizzazione dei documenti d’archivio è molto arretrata [...]. Dalla pandemia molti archivi, soprattutto archivi di Stato, italiani hanno iniziato a digitalizzare gli inventari e pubblicarli.”

Libraries [...] that have ancient collections are more attuned to the theme of resources digitisation [...] there still are big lacunae [...] only a small fraction of these materials is digitised, and online catalogues are also lacking⁸⁸.

Digitising the most ancient and famous ones, the treasures of public conservation institutions, would be something, but human resources are missing, competences are missing. But for us doing this kind of research it would be fundamental, it would be a turning point⁸⁹.

5.3.2 *The other materials*

With the notable exception of critical editions, most **publications** have both a print and digital publication, although they are anchored in the “print-paradigm” we have mentioned before (Edmond 2019).

The use of **digital catalogues, databases and other search tools** is almost universal among researchers in our sample, even those who tend to have a more traditional output (e.g., philologists and literary scholars).

Unpublished material, modern or contemporary, are usually never digitised. For more on the difficulties around digitising this kind of resources, see [section 5.6](#).

Personal data, on the one hand, and **documentation and standard**, on the other, are all in digital format in our sample (although, in principle, could be on a physical medium).

Corpora are all digital in our sample and are reported to be increasingly so, across the disciplines that use them.

5.3.3 *The impact of technology in “traditional” humanities workflows*

More than one interviewee commented on how technology has changed their way of working:

This job has deeply changed in these last years. It is faster to find anything, you do not have to visit a thousand libraries⁹⁰.

Now it is easier, we used to work by photocopying everything⁹¹.

⁸⁸ “[L]e biblioteche [...] che hanno fondi antichi sono più avanti rispetto al tema della digitalizzazione delle fonti anche [...] con delle lacune enormi [...] non solo una minima parte di questi materiali sono digitalizzati ma anche i cataloghi on line mancano.”

⁸⁹ “Digitalizzare quelli più antichi quelli più famosi quelli che fanno un po’ il tesoro di un ente pubblico di conservazione sarebbe già qualcosa ma mancano le risorse umane, mancano le capacità e mancano le risorse umane. Invece per noi che facciamo ricerca questo sarebbe fondamentale, sarebbe la svolta”.

⁹⁰ “[...] è un lavoro che è profondamente cambiato in questi anni. Si fa prima a trovare le cose, non devi più andare per mille biblioteche”.

⁹¹ “Adesso è più semplice, una volta facevamo le fotocopie, lavoravamo facendo le fotocopie di tutto [...]”.

[...] and we saw it during lockdown: if we had not had these [digital] instruments we could not have kept doing research⁹².

In 1 case, technology is seen as pushing methodological boundaries:

Our idea is to digitise everything and do way more advanced research⁹³.

Only 2 participants expressed some resistance, stating that technology is useful only to a degree. One simply mentioned that reading on paper is still unparalleled for them, while the other made a more substantial point, stating that “reading on-screen is not enough for philologists”:

[...] because reflection is necessary, the digital part is very important and can be really useful, even to structure the edition and show things, but then it is necessary to keep printing and reading [on paper], not only for the pleasure of it, but because some in-depth analysis can only be done on that kind of support⁹⁴.

Then added:

some things can better seen online, but in long-form reading some things are lost, the attention declines⁹⁵.

All in all, across our sample, **digital research tools and digital representations of cultural objects are extensively used**. There is some resistance to the replacement of physical printed books with digital publications, which are seen by a small minority of researchers (2/19) as changing the way of approaching a written text.

⁹² “[...] e lo abbiamo visto durante il lockdown, se non avessimo avuto questi strumenti [digitali] non avremmo potuto proseguire la nostra ricerca”.

⁹³ “Insomma la nostra idea è quella di digitalizzare tutto e di portare avanti una ricerca che sia molto più avanzata”.

⁹⁴ “[...] perché è necessaria la riflessione, la parte digitale è importantissima può essere anche molto utile, anche per strutturarla l’edizione per fare vedere delle cose, ma poi è necessario che il libro si continui a stampare e che si legga non solo per il piacere della lettura, ma perché alcuni approfondimenti si possono fare solo su un supporto che è di quel tipo lì”.

⁹⁵ “Online alcune cose si vedono meglio, ma nella lettura lunga si perdono delle cose, cioè l’attenzione si abbassa [...]”.

5.4 Documentation, standards, and methodologies

As mentioned above, we split question 3 into 3 parts. Here, we discuss questions 3b and 3c, which revolve around documentation, standards, and methodologies. The first one asked “Are [these materials] usually accompanied by documentation? Are there standards recognised in your discipline regarding these materials?”. The second one asked: “And, speaking of standards and good practices, are there recognised, frequently applied methodologies in your discipline? And are they somehow described or formalised?”⁹⁶.

We have bundled these two together because most interviewees (11/19), when hearing the word “standard” started talking about the methodologies they perceived as the standard in their discipline, *de facto* answering to the following question.

5.4.1 Documentation and standards

When asked about whether the materials mentioned earlier in the interview had any accompanying **documentation**, 4 researchers responded “yes”. In 3 cases, they referred to:

- **software documentation** and **deliverables** for the project’s funders (1),
- deliverables for funders only (1),
- **internal documentation**, restricted to the project participants (1).

The fourth researcher talked about database tables containing metadata and constituting the main documentation of the project. This observation, although interesting, uses the term “documentation” in a slightly broader sense than the one we are adopting here: it refers to metadata rather “paradata”, or data describing the methods of data generation/collection.

The rest of the sample answered negatively or simply ignored this part of the question.

The situation is not dissimilar if we look at **standards**. At the time of the interview, we chose not to define the word, letting researchers free to interpret it as they pleased. Most interviewees (11) understood it in a broad sense and proceeded to describe how their discipline does indeed have “standard” methodologies, recognised across the field. We discuss these answers in [section 5.4.2](#) below.

Three interviewees simply responded there are no standards in their field, while 3 more briefly mentioned archival and museum standards in relation to the primary sources of their research, held and catalogued in conservation institutions, but without any real connection to their own research.

Finally, 2 researchers responded that they do follow specific standards in their research:

- **web standards** in 1 case (they mentioned JSON, RDF, XML, OWL),

⁹⁶ To read the untranslated questions in Italian, and how they compare to Thoegersen’s, see [section 3.1](#).

- **cataloguing and technical standards** to ensure interoperability between databases in the other.

Regarding this last point, the interviewee pointed out that some European projects are indeed working on shared standards, but that interoperability is often an afterthought, and this leads to a duplication of efforts:

To be fair there used to be more discussion on this years ago, before Covid, than today; there is a certain resignation to the fact that [...] everybody uses their own system⁹⁷.

As we have seen in [section 5.2](#), we have included both documentation and standards in our list of materials, although **these concepts** – at least in their more specific, technical sense – **seem to be familiar only to a small subset of researchers, all of which do not belong to the philology and literary criticism disciplinary area.**

5.4.2 Methodologies

The interviewees in our sample did not shy away from discussing their methodologies and provided a wealth of information on the subject. To simplify matters, I have decided to analyse the 4 disciplinary areas⁹⁸ separately. Some observations, however, are transversal to more than one of them. In particular:

- **methodologies are formalized in manuals:**

Somebody worked on it but specifically in connection with teaching, there are some texts that have the aim of introducing university students to the various methodologies⁹⁹.

There are manuals indicating the editorial techniques and the mistakes to avoid [...] there are volumes that have become milestones [...]. It is a methodology that has stratified, that has been fine-tuned more and more and now is formalised in these volumes¹⁰⁰.

Methodologies to prepare a critical apparatus exist and are formalised in manuals¹⁰¹.

⁹⁷ “A dire la verità alcuni anni fa, prima del Covid, se ne discuteva più di quanto se ne faccia oggi in cui c’è una certa rassegnazione al fatto che, [...] ognuno fa un po’ con il suo sistema”.

⁹⁸ For a description of how we categorised scholars into macro-disciplines, please see [section 3.2](#).

⁹⁹ “Qualcuno se ne è occupato ma in modo soprattutto legato alla didattica, ci sono alcuni testi che con l’intento di introdurre effettivamente gli studenti universitari alle varie metodologie sicuramente hanno lavorato”.

¹⁰⁰ “Sì sul lato dell’edizione ci sono dei manuali [...] in cui si indica qual è la tecnica editoriale e quindi quali siano le prassi da seguire e gli errori da evitare [...] ci sono alcuni volumi che sono un po’ delle pietre miliari [...]. Quindi è tutta una metodologia che si è stratificata, che poi è stata anche messa a punto in modo sempre più preciso e che si trova ormai formalizzata in questi volumi”.

¹⁰¹ “Metodologie per la preparazione di un apparato critico di un edizione critica sì esistono sono formalizzate nella manualistica”.

- the **teacher-student relationship is important** in establishing methodologies:

Formalised? I'm thinking this formalisation happens very early, while being formed, even at university level [...]. It is an unwritten rule, deposited through practice¹⁰².

[...] the work done together, also the discussions and progress made within each unit [...] they are useful to the enrichment of culture in general and need to be safeguarded. Although it is invisible, because it relies on the teacher's competences or, in any case, on more knowledgeable people transmitting it down to younger people¹⁰³.

- importance of **multi-disciplinarity**:

Our discipline tries to be inter-disciplinary [...]. Manufacts are often complex, and it is possible to understand more by putting together different specialists¹⁰⁴.

We are working to shed light on this from a multi-disciplinary perspective, so not only with traditional methods¹⁰⁵.

A research field like romance philology is comparative, multi-disciplinary, brings to fruition many different know-hows¹⁰⁶.

For more insight on how researchers collaborate with colleagues, please see [section 5.5.1](#).

When we asked researchers at FICLIT whether their work is based on a precise, recognised, methodology the vast majority immediately replied “yes”. This is probably **one of the most surprising aspects of this analysis**. Even among philologists and literary critics, which we could argue are more “traditional” than researchers working in, e.g., linguistics or archival and library studies, **a staggering 11 out of 12 interviewees stated they had a precise methodology**.

The situation is more nuanced as far as the description and formalisation of these methods is concerned: we certainly are a long way away from workflows¹⁰⁷ that are “explicit [...] documented and, therefore verifiable” (Edmond 2019, p. 15), but these answers seem to suggest that humanists might be ready for this kind of discussion. We are now going to look, in the next 5 sections, at discipline-specific reflections on methodology.

¹⁰² “Formalizzata? Mi viene da pensare che questa formalizzazione avvenga molto presto, cioè a livello di formazione e addirittura nei corsi d'Università [...] è una legge non scritta depositata attraverso la pratica”.

¹⁰³ “Il lavoro fatto insieme anche nelle discussioni e nel progresso di ciascuna unità [...] serve alla crescita della cultura complessiva quindi questa è una cosa da salvaguardare ma questo è un prodotto invisibile perché sono le competenze che ha un maestro o comunque chi ne sa di più trasmette ai più giovani”.

¹⁰⁴ “[L]a nostra disciplina prova ad essere interdisciplinare [...]. Spesso i manufatti sono complessi e quindi si capiscono più cose mettendo assieme specialisti diversi”.

¹⁰⁵ “[N]oi ci stiamo adoperando affinché si possa gettare la luce da un punto di vista multidisciplinare e quindi non solo usando i metodi tradizionali”.

¹⁰⁶ “Una ricerca come la filologia romanza [è] comparativa, pluridisciplinare [...] mette a frutto molti saperi diversi”.

¹⁰⁷ While workflows often have a specific connotation, as something systematic and streamlined, we use the term as equivalent to methodology in this context.

5.4.2.1 Philology and literary criticism

As we have seen, most researchers in our cohort (12/19) belong to the field of philology and literary criticism. As such, reflections on methodologies are way richer and more varied than in the other areas below.

We find a **multiplicity of methodologies**, which is nothing new and reflects long-standing disciplinary distinctions:

- philology of copy (centred on the text): multiplicity of witnesses, Lachmann's method, *stemma codicum*, *recentio*, etc.;
- new philology (centred on the document): diplomatic approach, drawing also from palaeography and papyrology;
- authorial philology: single witness, written by the hand of the author;
- comparative philology, spanning different languages and cultures.

These distinctions however are not clear-cut, and many **researchers state they mix and match between methodologies** according to the type of tradition that carries the literary work under study.

Of the 12 interviewees in this disciplinary area, 8 published critical editions (see [section 5.2.1](#)) and 10 described them as the main, although by no means the only, type of publication in their field¹⁰⁸. **Critical editions are deeply formalized research outputs:**

The critical edition of a document absolutely follows criteria that have consolidated across the years¹⁰⁹.

Within a critical edition I expect to find the text presented in a specific way, an apparatus compiled in a specific way, and I know the type of information I'm going to find there¹¹⁰.

I can follow this or that rule [...], or even propose modifications, but of course there are parameters to evaluate if a critical edition is scientifically sound or not¹¹¹.

These editions have a precise structure, although there are "margins to experiment", as the primary sources being edited are extremely varied. They usually include these elements, among others:

- the critical text, often with numbered lines,

¹⁰⁸ One of them mentioned at the same time that the outputs of research are becoming more varied: "Beyond the book you can find exhibitions, in person or online, videos, documentaries, everything that is defined as 'dissemination', 'third mission', aimed to non-specialists" ("Al di là del libro ci possono essere mostre, fisicamente o on line, si possono realizzare dei video, documentari, tutto quello che viene definito disseminazione, quindi rivolto a una terza missione, cioè divulgazione verso non specialisti [...]").

¹⁰⁹ "L'edizione critica del documento segue assolutamente dei criteri che ormai si sono consolidati da molti anni".

¹¹⁰ "Io mi aspetto di trovare in un'edizione critica il testo presentato in un certo modo, un apparato fatto in un determinato modo, e so che in quell'apparato troverò determinate informazioni".

¹¹¹ "[P]osso attenermi a una regola o a un'altra [...], oppure proporre dei correttivi ma certo che esistono dei parametri per valutare se un'edizione è scientifica oppure no".

- a double apparatus, one usually devoted to variants and the other to critical and philological comments,
- a list of all manuscripts and print witnesses,
- a *stemma codicum* (where applicable),
- bibliographical references for each witness,
- notes and comments, both more general (e.g., to describe editorial criteria and interpretative choices made) and specific to single lines.

Critical editions are indeed the expression of a methodology: they present an hypothesis (the critically reconstructed text) but also a description of the steps taken to formulate such hypothesis (apparatus, *stemma*, notes, comments). Their structure and wealth of methodological information make these editions suitable to an extremely specialised audience (“Since it is a critical edition is obviously very difficult it will ever be read by non-specialists”¹¹²), unlike reading editions that include only the critically reconstructed text and are usually meant for a broader audience. For more on research materials’ target audience, see [section 5.5.2](#).

Further, when asked whether their work is based on a precise methodology, recognised across the field, the vast majority of philologists and literary critics in our sample (11/12) immediately replied “yes”. Here are some of the strongest and most interesting statements in this direction:

Absolutely, the discipline has its standards that are shared, even very formal standards because classical philology is really interested in the formal aspects¹¹³.

First of all, the Lachmannian method and then [...] other criteria, still shared, in the sense that we never proceed casually but we all follow the same methodology¹¹⁴.

We also have a method, some forget about it, but a “bad” article is an article that has not followed the method, that advances hypotheses that cannot be demonstrated, that has logical loopholes¹¹⁵.

One researcher went even further, stating:

I am a philologist, so I’m the closest to science. Criticism is further away, there clearly is more freedom of choice [...]. Those who work in philology are closer to scientists and move in a less extemporaneous way, we have templates¹¹⁶.

¹¹² “Trattandosi di un’edizione critica è chiaro che difficilmente l’edizione critica viene letta da non specialisti”.

¹¹³ “Assolutamente, la disciplina ha i suoi standard che sono condivisi, standard anche molto formali perché la filologia classica comunque è assolutamente attenta ai dati formali [...]”.

¹¹⁴ “Prima di tutto il metodo Lachmanniano e dopodiché [...] dei criteri altri che sono sempre condivisi, nel senso che non andiamo a caso ma seguiamo tutti la stessa metodologia.”

¹¹⁵ “Anche noi abbiamo un metodo, alcuni se ne dimenticano, però se un articolo è ‘brutto’ è un articolo che non ha seguito il metodo, che accampa ipotesi di lavoro che non sono dimostrabili, che ha falle di logica”.

¹¹⁶ “Io sono una filologa quindi la cosa più vicina alle scienze. Perché la critica è più lontana evidentemente c’è un arbitrio maggiore [...] coloro che si occupano di filologia sono [...] più vicino agli scienziati e ci muoviamo in maniera meno estemporanea [...], abbiamo delle griglie”.

This comparison between philology and criticism is not brought up by any other interviewee and remains an isolated comment. However, interestingly, the only researcher in this disciplinary area who stated that they do not follow a method is indeed a literary critic, who questioned the very idea of a method:

I do not believe in a pre-constituted method, I come from a school that did not believe in it [...] so I believe that even the sciences do not have a pre-constituted method, that big discoveries happen through infringing on a method¹¹⁷.

As far as the **description and formalisation** of these methods is concerned, the situation is more nuanced. As we have seen before, some researchers commented that the methodology is formalised in university manuals, as well as in preceding works that have become “milestones”, while others described it as “deposited through practice”. One researcher commented that their specific field is fairly new to Italian universities and its theorisation is ongoing¹¹⁸, while another said that their methodology is changing due to technological advances¹¹⁹.

5.4.2.2 Language and linguistics

Four researchers of the total 19 participants have been assigned to this disciplinary area, which covers linguistics, but also language teaching and translation studies¹²⁰.

Methodological reflections by these 4 researchers can be summarised as follows:

- there are **many different methodologies**, since the discipline is quite broad and includes very different approaches:

for example, in psycholinguistics and neurolinguistics [...] the protocols are close to those of the experimental sciences in the medical field, the works have to be understood by both teams. [...] historical linguistics has more traditional methods, only partly codified¹²¹.

¹¹⁷ “Quindi io non credo in un metodo preconstituito però questa è un’opinione personale, vengo da una scuola che non credeva nel metodo preconstituito [...] quindi credo che un metodo preconstituito neanche la scienza l’abbia, nel senso che le grandi scoperte avvengono attraverso l’infrazione del metodo”.

¹¹⁸ “The theorisation of the discipline is ongoing [...] I think we often work implicitly, linking back to other disciplines [...]” (“La teorizzazione della disciplina è ancora in corso [...]. Mi sembra che si lavori molto sull’implicito, rimandando a formazione di altre discipline [...].”).

¹¹⁹ “The recognised method is still linked to paper catalogues, and we are bringing it into the XXI century with great perseverance” (“Il metodo riconosciuto è ancora quello del catalogo cartaceo e noi lo stiamo portando nel ventunesimo secolo con grande tenacia”).

¹²⁰ Again, see [section 3.2](#).

¹²¹ “Per esempio, in psicolinguistica e neurolinguistica [...] il tipo di protocolli si avvicinano molto a quelli delle scienze sperimentali di ambito medico, cioè i lavori devono essere leggibili da entrambe le squadre. [...] la linguistica storica vive di metodi più tradizionali solo in parte codificati”.

- **best practices are often more important than theoretical considerations**, due to the applied nature of the discipline:

The exchange of best practices is very important, even more than theoretical elaboration, and often goes in parallel with experimentation, since this is a very practical discipline¹²².

- **the formalization of these methodologies is scarce**:

It is still left to the good will of individual scholars¹²³.

I wouldn't say there is a standard [...] but there certainly are recurring elements¹²⁴.

- there is a **combination of qualitative and quantitative analysis**;
- **data is rarely (but increasingly) shared** together with aggregated results, and this is often due to privacy concerns:

We have always published aggregated data; it is not yet standard for us to make available the database and then generalise in the publications, but we are definitely moving in that direction¹²⁵.

The materials, the recordings, are interesting but I cannot ask [participants] to sign a blanket consent [...] because I would risk decimating the, already few, people who are enthusiast to participate [...] the dissemination will thus be limited¹²⁶.

- other **ethical concerns** revolve around the ownership of linguistic data.

Generally, within this small group, there seems to be an interest in sharing research data¹²⁷, tempered by a concern regarding the privacy of speakers and the extra work involved in making them available. For more on these last points, see [section 5.6](#).

5.4.2.3 History of art

Only 1 researcher in our sample belongs to this discipline. As such, these observations can hardly be considered representative, but are nonetheless interesting:

- **audio-visual materials are fundamental**,
- there are **different approaches** (the interviewee own method is close to historiography),

¹²² "Lo scambio di buone pratiche ha un ruolo molto importante, più anche delle elaborazioni teoriche, che spesso poi essendo una disciplina che ha un carattere molto pratico [...] nasce in parallelo alle sperimentazioni".

¹²³ "È ancora molto lasciato alla buona volontà e alla serietà dei singoli".

¹²⁴ "Non direi che c'è uno standard [...] però ci sono degli elementi del tutto ricorrenti [...]".

¹²⁵ "Abbiamo sempre pubblicato dei dati aggregati, da noi non è ancora standard, ma ci si sta muovendo molto in questa direzione, il fatto che si metta a disposizione database di cui poi si danno le generalizzazioni nelle pubblicazioni".

¹²⁶ "I materiali, le registrazioni [...] sono interessanti però io a loro non farò firmare una liberatoria generale sul fatto che ci faccio quello che mi pare perché rischierei di decimare i già pochi entusiasti di partecipare a una cosa così. [...] la diffusione sarà limitata in questo modo".

¹²⁷ "The idea, as always, is to ensure the maximum sharing not only of the results, but also of study materials" ("L'idea è come sempre di rendere possibile il massimo della condivisione non soltanto dei risultati ma anche dei materiali di studio").

- **“visual philology” provides a “fundamental methodological basis”:**

I consider fundamental the aspect that I would call our philology, the evaluation [...], it is a real visual analysis [...]. I believe it is the fundamental basis of our discipline, we all share the same templates to recognise different styles, different languages [...]. Because “visual philology” is proper philology, otherwise it is easy to make mistakes¹²⁸.

In closing, this researcher added that they have always be drawn to critical and philological studies for their methodological clarity and structure, confirming the perception that philologists in our sample have of themselves:

I always felt something was missing from the methodological perspective, I felt there was not enough clarity [...]. This is why I have always counted on italianists, literary scholars, where I always saw a strong disciplinary structure that helped me; it is not casual if I work well in this department¹²⁹.

5.4.2.4 Computer science

We interviewed only 1 researcher in computer science, a discipline that unsurprisingly is only marginally represented within the department. The reflections that emerged are:

- there are **clear methodologies and paradigms** that are “mixed and matched” according to each project needs,
- **methodological choices are documented** in software documentation and deliverables,
- **underlying data are sometimes published**, and their use can be tracked,
- **pre-existing code is reused** and modified to meet the project need.

5.4.2.5 Archival and library studies

Finally, 1 researcher working in archival and library studies shared these considerations with us:

- **shared methodologies exist**,
- **methodologies are not particularly formalised**, one of the reasons being that all archives are unique, and some have been built over centuries¹³⁰.

¹²⁸ “Io reputo assolutamente fondamentale l’aspetto che io chiamerei la nostra filologia, ossia la valutazione [...] è un’analisi visiva proprio autoptica. [...] sinceramente credo che sia la base metodologica fondamentale della nostra disciplina, sulla quale tutti quanti noi condividiamo le griglie di riconoscimento degli stili, dei diversi linguaggi. [...] Perché la filologia del vedere è una filologia a tutti gli effetti, o si prendono granchi altrimenti”.

¹²⁹ “Ho sempre sentito una gravissima carenza nell’ambito metodologico, cioè sentivo poca chiarezza [...] tant’è che mi sono appoggiata agli studiosi di italianistica, di letteratura, dove invece vedevo una fortissima struttura disciplinare che mi ha aiutato; infatti, non per caso mi trovo bene in questo dipartimento”.

¹³⁰ “Every archive is a unique deposit of memory that has stratified across centuries according to the specific informational needs; archival practices are the most diverse, they can vary a lot from institute to institute” (“Ciascun archivio è esso stesso un deposito di memoria unico che si è stratificato nel corso dei secoli sulla base di esigenze informative, di prassi archivistiche che sono le più diverse, posso variare fortemente da istituto ad istituto”).

5.5 Granting access to colleagues and to the public

In question 4 we asked: “Who can access these materials, and do you share them (or would share them) with colleagues and other researchers? And with the public at large (e.g., online)?”¹³¹. There are 3 separate aspects to look at here, one relating to collaboration and sharing between colleagues, one relating to the target audience of research outputs, and one to the accessibility of research materials, both used and produced. Let us see them in turn.

5.5.1 Collaboration and sharing

Collaboration seems to be pivotal in our sample of researchers. In many cases (9/19), such collaboration entails consulting other researchers, belonging to the same disciplinary field:

We typically read each other’s work, selecting one or two trusted colleagues – that is the first kind of sharing¹³².

In other instances, it helps foster inter-disciplinarity:

This is an element where our discipline tries to be interdisciplinary, [...] trusting, when necessary, other people’s competence¹³³.

However, this is described by one of our interviewees, and we tend to agree, as “**not systematic and not ‘real’ sharing**” because it comes down to asking for feedback and suggestions rather than opening up to real collaboration:

It is not systematic, and it is not real sharing, maybe you ask somebody knowledgeable on the topic for advice, sharing is something else, is letting somebody else into your own research project¹³⁴.

This type of collaboration through consultation is often informal and it is not recognised within academia, beyond the occasional acknowledgment within the final publication.

It is perhaps surprising that **even more researchers in our sample (12/19), across all disciplinary areas, state that they work, or have worked, in team with others**, mostly colleagues, or sometimes PhD and master’s students. Although a couple of them state that they “like working alone” or that “philologists often work alone”, they still consider teamwork “extremely useful and productive”, at least in some specific projects.

Only 1 researcher, who works in literary criticism, stood out from the rest of the sample by stating:

¹³¹ To read the untranslated question in Italian, and how it compares to Thoegersen’s, see [section 3.1](#).

¹³² “[T]ipicamente noi ci leggiamo fra noi le cose; si individua uno o due colleghi nei quali si ripone fiducia scientifica ma anche capacità di correggere, quella è una prima condivisione”.

¹³³ “[...] è un elemento nel quale la nostra disciplina prova ad essere interdisciplinare, [...] affidarci quando è necessario alla competenza di altre persone”.

¹³⁴ “[...] non in modo sistematico e non è una vera condivisione, chiedi magari a qualcuno che si è occupato di un argomento dei consigli, la condivisione è qualcosa di diverso, è quando uno entra proprio nella tua ricerca e collabora con te”.

Normally I do not share my work materials with anybody, and my colleagues do the same, perhaps we are a bit too archaic. There is no sharing, but rather a 'top secret' kind of approach. [...] I also have colleagues who fear their ideas might be stolen [...], sharing is neither habitual nor common for us¹³⁵.

This is echoed by comments made by others, who do work in a team but note that "the individual contribution to research is sacrosanct". The **fear that research ideas might be stolen before publication**, on the other hand, is mentioned by 5 interviewees in total, and it is often **explicitly linked to research evaluation**:

It is better to keep the unpublished archival original to yourself, otherwise somebody can publish it before you¹³⁶.

The material is shared with very few people and only partially, not in its entirety, to protect the originality of the research and its novelty, which has to be made public only when the research is finished and complete¹³⁷.

Two researchers go on to say that current evaluation practices stifle collaboration and openness:

I would share research results with anybody but [...] as long as hiring, career progression and evaluation within universities [...] keep happening with the current parameters I am forced to use copyright protection and keep results inaccessible¹³⁸.

I like putting anything in common, but we face an issue of intellectual property since we mostly publish single-authorship articles, and our career is based on publications¹³⁹.

It seems possible to conclude that since collaboration, in the same way as peer review, is not taken into account at the level of research evaluation, **humanities scholars tend to work together but publish alone (or in very small groups)**.

Another interesting aspect that emerged at this stage, mentioned by 3 of the 19 interviewees, is that **teamwork within philology and literary criticism often entails a "horizontal", rather than a "vertical", division of labour**, where all team members do the same type of work in parallel:

¹³⁵ "Io normalmente il materiale del lavoro, e anche i miei colleghi sono così, forse siamo un po' troppo arcaici, non c'è la condivisione, c'è ancora questa idea del top secret. [...] ho anche colleghi che [...] temono il furto delle idee [...] non c'è l'abitudine, non è una consuetudine da noi condividere".

¹³⁶ "[L]'inedito d'archivio è meglio tenerlo per sé, questo ovviamente, perché altrimenti qualcuno te lo pubblica prima".

¹³⁷ "[I]l materiale viene condiviso con un pochissime persone e in modo parziale, non integrale, per tutelare l'originalità della ricerca e per tutelare la novità che deve essere comunicata solo quando la ricerca è terminata e compiuta".

¹³⁸ "[I] risultati della ricerca io li metterei aperti per tutti ma [...] se poi il reclutamento all'università, le progressioni di carriera la stessa valutazione della operatività o no di un ricercatore [...] continua ad avvenire con questi parametri, io sono obbligata a mantenere dei copyright e dunque a mantenere una non accessibilità dei risultati".

¹³⁹ "Io sono molto comunitario però c'è un problema di proprietà intellettuale visto che le nostre carriere si basano su articoli firmati prevalentemente a firma singola e le nostre carriere si legano alle pubblicazioni".

I coordinate with the others, but everyone looks at a sub-set of the manuscripts, otherwise it would be impossible for one person to deal with all of them¹⁴⁰.

Even when we do teamwork, we split work horizontally, the workload is portioned out and everyone does the same type of work. Unlike the vertical division we find in other disciplines [...], ours is an absolutely equal allocation of the workload¹⁴¹.

From a more practical standpoint, collaboration takes place through email and telephone communications, through cloud storage and file-sharing services (often Google Drive), or other specialised software (e.g., for corpus creation).

5.5.2 *The target audience of research results*

I have categorised the research materials produced by our interviewees according to their intended audience, based on what researchers told me in their respective interviews. I have broken down the categories used in [table 5.1](#) into more granular categories, as they often have different target audiences.

Table 5.4: Outputs of research by target audience

Intended for the general public	Intended for a specialised audience	Intended for a specific, restricted audience
reading editions*	critical editions	platform
ancillary websites	journal articles	deliverables
exhibitions	monographs or edited books	project notes
guided tours	essays	corpora
	conferences and workshops	personal data
	webinars	born-digital artifacts*
	teacher training	
	facsimiles and photographs	
	3D models	
	videos	
	mobile apps	
	3D web viewers	
	software	
	databases	

* Categorisation to take with a grain of salt. See the following paragraphs for a brief explanation of why.

The outputs listed in column 1 are intended for as broad a public as possible. Reading editions usually aim at popularising a new edition of a certain literary text; however, if the text is obscure and niche, they can be of interest only to a specialised public. The websites mentioned in our sample publicise a research project outside of the immediate scholarly community and are therefore intended for the public at large. Finally, events like exhibitions

¹⁴⁰ “[...] mi coordino con altre persone, ognuno si guarda dei manoscritti perché altrimenti sarebbe impossibile per una sola persona riuscire a guardarli tutti”.

¹⁴¹ “Anche quando noi pensiamo a progetti in team, alla fine la divisione è sempre orizzontale, di fatto il lavoro viene suddiviso in porzioni in cui il singolo individuo fa la stessa cosa non come la divisione verticale che c’è in altre discipline [...] è una divisione assolutamente paritaria la nostra”.

and tours fall within universities' "third mission" to contribute to the development of wider society.

The outputs listed in column 2 are usually of interest only to specialists, namely students and colleagues within the same, or a similar, discipline.

The outputs listed in the third column are created with a very specific audience in mind, which is more restricted than the community of specialists. In most of the cases brought to our attention by the study participants, this depends on privacy concerns. Please note that the situation around born-digital artifacts is rather complex and that they may be made more widely available, depending on who owns them and how they plan to use them.

We will see in the next section that **intended audience and level of accessibility are two rather separate aspects**. While outputs intended for a restricted audience are of course kept under lock and key, those intended for a specialised audience can be freely available or not, depending on the type of output and project funding. Outputs intended for the public are intellectually more accessible than the others but are rarely available for free.

5.5.3 Accessing research materials

The following table lists all research materials as categorised in [section 5.2.3](#), together with an assessment on their level of accessibility as derived from the interviews. Below, we add some details, where available.

Table 5.5: Outputs of research by accessibility

Research output	Assessment on accessibility in our sample
software	freely available online
standards	
websites	
born-digital artifacts	usually freely available online but access may be restricted
catalogues, databases and other search tools	
digital infrastructures	
documentation	usually freely accessible to anybody in public spaces or conservation institutes
monuments, artworks, unique artifacts	
ancient manuscripts and early printed books	
archival documents	usually accessible to scholars within conservation institutes, under supervision (unless particularly frail/damaged)
unpublished materials (modern or contemporary)	
digital representation of cultural objects	if published at all, they are usually freely available online; otherwise, permission to publish must be sought and can be expensive
events	may require registration and relevant specialisation*
publications	mostly published in closed access
personal data	for internal use only
corpora	
* This is a personal evaluation and is not based on the interviews, as information on this point is missing.	

Software, produced and used by 2 of the projects described by participants, are **made available online**, often from the very start of the development process, using, e.g., GitHub. **Standards** are normally freely available online, together with their own documentation, to encourage uptake within the community of reference. Ancillary **websites** such as those described are freely accessible online, not behind a paywall.

Born-digital artifacts (tags, associations and texts produced by online users) can either be freely available or not, according to who owns them and what their intended use is; it is indeed difficult to generalise.

Unfortunately, we have not gathered any information on the level of accessibility of the **databases** populated as part of 2 research projects in our sample. As for **catalogues, and other search tools** used by the interviewees, the vast majority is available online, either freely or paid for by the university library services.

Looking at **documentation**:

- project notes are for internal use only as they may contain participants' personal data.

If we break down **digital infrastructures**, we find that:

- the mobile app is intended for a specialised public but is available for anyone to download for free;
- the 3D web viewer is also available to anyone online;
- the platform is open only to selected institutions.

Monuments, artworks and unique artifacts are usually accessible to the wider public. Sometimes the objects of interest to the research project can be scattered in different museums and conservation institutes around the world. In some cases, digitisation campaigns with the aim of making museums' holdings more accessible have started, although the process is complex and expensive (see below).

Ancient manuscripts and early printed books are usually accessible only to scholars within conservation institutes. The process often requires special care (gloves, bookrest) and is supervised. If the conservation institute is a public library, pictures can be taken exclusively for research purposes. Sometimes, the materials of interest can be scattered around the world, even in war areas, making them available only upon digitisation (see below).

Archival documents are rarely digitised and usually need to be viewed in person. The same applies to archive inventories, although some State archives have started digitising and publishing them online during the pandemic.

Unpublished materials (such as drawings, letters, photographs) are usually accessible only to scholars within conservation institutes. They are rarely digitised and sometimes are not

even catalogued. The originals must be handled with extreme care and their publication, in part or in full, requires the express authorization of the author, or their heirs, if still alive (on this, see [section 5.6](#)).

We have seen before that **digital representation of cultural objects** have been produced as part of 4 projects,

- in 2 cases were kept for internal use and not shared with anyone,
- in 1 case facsimiles and 3D models were produced and made freely available online,
- in another, videos were also made freely available online.

For a discussion on the use of digitised cultural objects in research, please refer to [section 5.3.1](#).

As far as **events** are concerned, exhibitions and guided tours usually require registration, but do not limit access in any other way. Conferences, workshops, webinars and teacher training, on the other hand, may or may not restrict registration to people with a relevant specialisation. Unfortunately, we did not delve into this aspect during the interviews, and we cannot make any statements with confidence.

If we look in more detail at the **publications produced** by our sample of researchers, we see that:

- all 8 critical editions mentioned in the interviews are published on paper, in closed access, and with a traditional publisher; they are usually found in specialised libraries;
- only 1 out of 4 edited books has been published in open access for express wish of its authors;
- 2 out of 8 projects producing journal articles made them available in green open access according to funding requirements;
- the 2 reading editions mentioned are both published by traditional publishers in closed access, although their circulation in libraries is probably wider than that of other scholarly publications.

Publications used by our researchers as primary or secondary sources can be:

- published on paper and held in libraries, but digitised and freely available online, when out of copyright (up to the first half of the XX Century);
- published on paper (and sometimes digitally) but available exclusively through the university libraries that have paid for access;
- published digitally or subsequently digitised by their own authors, and made freely available online (e.g., contemporary teaching materials).

Personal data (produced by 2 projects) are protected by the GDPR regardless of the technology used for processing and need to be protected as they can lead to the identification of living individuals¹⁴² (European Commission 2022) (see also [section 5.6](#) below).

The **corpora** produced by researchers in our cohort are associated and/or contain personal and sensitive information. As such, they are not made available to anyone outside of the project team, due to privacy concerns. Our interviewees recognised that value of making these primary sources available to the research community and stated that the discipline is moving in that direction. However, they point to the added workload (to anonymise and make corpora interoperable) as the main obstacle in the context of their projects (again, see also [section 5.6](#) below).

5.6 Copyright and privacy

Question 5 revolves around security, privacy, and copyright: “Of the materials you have listed, are there any that contain confidential information or concern someone’s privacy? Are there intellectual property/copyright concerns? And security concerns?”¹⁴³.

No researcher mentioned issues relating to security, but they did cite concerns around copyright, on the one hand, and privacy, on the other.

Image copyright comes into play when researchers seek to publish digital representations of cultural objects such as facsimiles and photographs, e.g., as part of a scholarly publication. While some libraries and museums are more liberal, others require hefty fees for image publication and claim copyright on them, an issue that is currently very much debated in the GLAM community. We have seen in [section 5.3.1](#) that this is less of an issue for philologists or literary critics, who rarely include images in their publications, than for researchers working in other areas, such as art history. Please note that the 2 researchers who produced digital representations as part of their projects did so without claiming any rights on them.

A couple of researchers lament the **different copyright and privacy laws existing in different countries**, which complicate their work considerably, especially when international collaborations take place:

¹⁴² Fully anonymised data is not considered personal data. For a definition and more information see: https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/what-personal-data_en

¹⁴³ To read the untranslated question in Italian, and how it compares to Thoegersen’s, see [section 3.1](#).

Switzerland has different parameters from France, different from Italy, England and Germany, there is no European standard on this so everybody has to follow the rules of their department. This is a more general problem investing universities¹⁴⁴.

Another describes the **extra work done to avoid dealing with copyright issues**:

For example, I have added translations to make my work more accessible. I have translated everything because I did not want to face the issues of using somebody else's translation¹⁴⁵.

Only 1 researcher focused on their own intellectual property, describing how the **rights of scholarly publications are held by academic publishers and not by authors**, something that is described as "the norm". The situation is however different for works intended for a wider public, such as reading editions, which may be published by other, non-scholarly, publishers.

Some research materials reportedly do not present any issues for our pool of researchers, as far as copyright and privacy are concerned. These are:

- ancient manuscripts and early printed books,
- works published before the first half of the XX century,
- archival documents,
- databases,
- software,
- contemporary materials made freely available online, such as teaching materials.

Other materials are more problematic, especially contemporary unpublished materials, which require an **agreement with the authors' heirs or estate**. Apart from copyright, which may still be held by the heirs, these materials also present issues relating to privacy, as they often include personal information:

When studying letter exchanges among dead authors there is this problem, there is sensitive information, names of people that may be alive, or at least their relatives are¹⁴⁶.

This may lead to discarding certain documents, if they are not strictly necessary to answer the project's research questions:

I tend not to use them because they are not necessary and because they could hurt the privacy of somebody I was not able to contact¹⁴⁷.

¹⁴⁴ "La Svizzera ha parametri diversi dalla Francia, ha parametri diversi dall'Italia, dall'Inghilterra e dalla Germania quindi non c'è uno standard europeo su questo per cui ognuno è tenuto a obbedire alle regole del proprio dipartimento. Questo è un problema più generale che riguarda tutto il mondo dell'università".

¹⁴⁵ "Ad esempio io ho inserito delle traduzioni in questa opera perché volevo renderla accessibile, le traduzioni le ho fatte tutte io perché non volevo pormi il problema di utilizzare la traduzione di un altro".

¹⁴⁶ "Quando si affrontano gli scambi epistolari di autori scomparsi c'è questo problema, ci sono dati sensibili, ci sono informazioni, nomi di persone che magari sono ancora vive o comunque ci sono ancora i familiari".

¹⁴⁷ "Tendo a non utilizzarli perché non sono necessari per la mia ricerca e perché potrebbero ledere la privacy di qualcuno che non ho avuto modo di contattare o non sono riuscito a contattare".

The projects dealing with **personal data**, in connection with linguistic corpora or with born-digital artifacts, have opted to either **restrict access** to them (see [section 5.5.3](#)) and/or to have an **advisor** for privacy and ethical issues.

One researcher from the field of language and linguistics mentioned that the University of Bologna has organised a short course for researchers in the past, on how to deal with privacy issues. Although potentially very interesting, it was based exclusively on cases studies and examples drawn from biology and the medical sciences. In their opinion, these examples were hardly applicable in other research fields, and this constituted a turn-down for researchers in language and linguistics, but even more so for others:

[...] the theorising was based on data and their protection, and on privacy issues, with examples that were a bit of a turn-down, in my opinion, for anybody who was not from that field. [...] Data management is indeed relevant to me, but the university's offer was out of sync with my needs, and I imagine even more so with those of a historian, or a literary scholar, who may have the same concerns. There is a lot of work to do¹⁴⁸.

5.7 Saving and discarding

Question 6 asks: "How do you decide what research materials to keep or discard at the end of a research project? And those you keep, where do you keep them?"¹⁴⁹. All researchers but one (18/19) stated that they **keep most of the materials they use and produce during a research project**:

During the working process I tend to keep everything¹⁵⁰.

[...] they can turn out to be useful because we specialise on particular authors and we have to go back to them later, it would not make sense to delete these materials [...] nothing is totally discarded¹⁵¹".

Among the materials that are indeed discarded we find for example article drafts, notes, and synoptic tables.

The main reason researchers give for keeping materials is that they **can be useful both in teaching and for further research**:

¹⁴⁸ "[...] tutta la teorizzazione era basata sul dato e la sua protezione e dei dati legati alla privacy con esempi che erano abbastanza respingenti secondo me per chiunque non fosse di quell'ambito lì. [...] Ho delle esigenze rispetto alla gestione dei dati ma la proposta dell'Ateneo era fuori sincrono rispetto a quello che poteva essere un'utilità per me, ma immagino ancora di meno per uno storico o uno che si occupa di letteratura che invece ha problemi di questo tipo, c'è molto lavoro da fare".

¹⁴⁹ To read the untranslated question in Italian, and how it compares to Thøgersen's, see [section 3.1](#).

¹⁵⁰ "Durante il processo di lavorazione conservo un po' tutto".

¹⁵¹ "[...] possono comunque risultare utili perché noi ci specializziamo su alcuni autori e poi magari dobbiamo tornarci su, non avrebbe senso eliminare questi materiali [...] nulla va del tutto scartato".

The project I have followed [...] have always been linked one to the other so you do not really finish and throw everything away, there is always an element of going back to things that it may be useful to retrieve¹⁵².

I very often use materials from previous or ongoing research projects in my teaching¹⁵³.

As a matter of fact, 1 research project in our sample started from the “residues of research done [by someone else] with a different focus”.

Finally, 4 interviewees stated that they keep a very **organised archive**¹⁵⁴:

I have my personal archiving systems, I have spaces in my external drives in which I put things I have finished working on. I tend not to throw anything away; I also like to keep the intermediate working stages because they can often be useful¹⁵⁵.

I catalogue everything and have an enormous archive¹⁵⁶.

Only 2 researchers describe how they have used **an open repository** in the past, in both cases Zenodo, although 1 researcher laments that it “does not reflect the complexity of humanities disciplines”:

It is not well articulated for the disciplinary complexities that research requires. You upload pre-prints, you upload spreadsheets, but for the humanities uploading pre-prints is not the most useful thing you can do¹⁵⁷.

All other participants seem to be storing their research materials in digital form **on their own devices**, using external hard drives, or on **commercial cloud storage services** (Google Drive and Dropbox being the most commonly mentioned).

Three researchers raise concerns about the **long-term preservation** of these materials. One of them underlines that there is a “cultural problem”:

[...] we only have temporary platforms. There is a cultural problem around how to preserve information in time and how to preserve the preservation platforms themselves, and to whom is given responsibility for their conservation and protection¹⁵⁸.

¹⁵² “I progetti che ho seguito [...] sono sempre stati un po’ concatenati l’uno con l’altro quindi non è che si chiude e si butta via tutto c’è sempre un riprendere delle cose che può essere utile recuperare”.

¹⁵³ “Io uso spessissimo materiali dalle ricerche che ho fatto o che sono in corso per fare didattica”.

¹⁵⁴ On the contrary, 1 interviewee lamented their terrible organization, which has led to repeated data losses in the past.

¹⁵⁵ “Ho i miei sistemi personali di archiviazione quindi ho i miei spazi in dischi esterni in cui le cose terminate vengono messe tendenzialmente non butto nulla mi piace anche conservare le fasi di lavorazione perché spesso possono tornare utili”.

¹⁵⁶ “Io schedo tutto e ho un archivio enorme”.

¹⁵⁷ “Non è articolata nella complessità disciplinare che la ricerca richiede per cui di fatto si caricano dei pre-print, si caricano dei fogli di dati, ma l’utilità nelle materia umanistiche non è quella di caricare pre-print”.

¹⁵⁸ “[...] non abbiamo se non delle piattaforme temporanee. Questo è un problema culturale di come le informazioni si conservano nel tempo e di come anche gli stessi portali si conservano nel tempo, cioè a chi è data la possibilità di conservarli e di proteggerli.”

while another was more concerned about **technical obsolescence**, which might prevent someone from recovering what they have been storing for years or decades.

To conclude, I want to quote another interviewee, who underlined how the “processes”, as they call them, the **intermediate stages of any projects are perhaps the most important thing to preserve**:

[...] the best thing to preserve is the work, everything in research that you cannot see [...]. I would save the processes, too, so it would be very difficult to discard anything, maybe I would discard the refuse, the preparatory materials. [...] I believe that, especially when you work in a digital environment, the problem of preserving the intermediate stages is important because sometimes they are also relevant¹⁵⁹.

5.8 Are your research materials data?

Questions 7 asked: “Lately there is a lot of talk about ‘open data’ and ‘research data’. Think back at the materials we talked about; would you consider any of them ‘data’? If so, which ones?”. It is a direct translation of the original question by Thoegersen, with an added mention of open data, to help researchers contextualise this complex question¹⁶⁰.

5.8.1 “Yes, they are”

When confronted with this question, **13 of the 19 researchers immediately responded “yes”** and proceeded to enumerate exactly which materials they consider to be data. Keep in mind that across this first sub-section and in the table below we refer exclusively to the first response that was given, and that many researchers expanded or restricted their first definition later in the interview.

Table 5.6: Which materials are data? First responses

Which materials are data?	N. of researchers (tot. 19)
all of them*	5
primary sources	3
primary sources and publications	1
primary sources, transcriptions, and publications	1
edited text and variants	1
quantitative and biographical data only	1
research results	1
* In 1 case, the researcher said: “I guess, I struggle with it, but yes, they’re data” (“Quello che mi sento di dire, faccio fatica, ma sì sono dei dati”), showing a clear unease with their answer.	

¹⁵⁹ “[...] la migliore cosa da conservare è il lavoro e anche tutto quello che non si vede della ricerca [...]. Salvarei anche i processi e quindi sarebbe molto difficile scartare delle cose, scarterei proprio le scorie cioè i materiali preparatori. [...] io credo che, soprattutto lavorando in ambienti digitali, il problema di come conservare anche le fasi intermedie sia importante perché delle volte anche le fasi intermedie sono significative”.

¹⁶⁰ Please note that interviewees already knew that the project revolved around open data and open science, since it had briefly been mentioned in the e-mail invitations. To read the untranslated question in Italian, and how it compares to Thoegersen’s, see [section 3.1](#).

One researcher did not answer the question directly, but raised an important point: citing Marc Bloch, he said that “data become data when somebody starts to pay attention to them” and added that his own research materials would have not been considered worthy of academic publication in the past (“they were not considered data for literary history, [...] they did not reach the dignity of literary texts”).¹⁶¹ He and his colleagues, he concluded, would try and **transform these scattered resources into data**. I think we should probably include this interviewer among those who see their own research results, and perhaps also their primary sources, as data.

This idea that researchers are somehow involved in “creating” their data was echoed by another researcher, who stated that “data is not simply what we see, but the reason why we see it the way we do”¹⁶².

5.8.2 “No, they are not”

Two researchers answered that they did not deal with data in their research project:

- 1 responded that their project did not use, or produce, any data **because it lacked any digital component**¹⁶³;
- the other stated: “mine are materials, **we do not have research data *strictu sensu*, in a technical sense**”¹⁶⁴.

5.8.3 “I do not know”

Three researchers responded they **did not know whether to consider their own research materials as data**. One of them cited ignorance of technology as a reason:

I don't know because I don't know much about technology¹⁶⁵.

Among those who answered “no” or “I do not know”, the concept of data is perceived as linked to the digital, or technological, sphere. We have encountered this idea briefly in the literature review ([section 2.3.4](#)), where the term “data” in its current, broader, meaning was indeed linked to the advent of digital technology (Avanço, Giglia, Gingold 2021, p. 7).

¹⁶¹ “I dati cominciano ad essere [tali] quando qualcuno presta attenzione. Tutti questi testi di cui noi abbiamo parlato per la grandissima maggioranza dei casi non erano considerati dati per la storia della letteratura [...], non erano testi che avevano acquisito la dignità di testi letterari”.

¹⁶² “Il dato non è semplicemente quello che vediamo ma perché lo vediamo come lo vediamo”.

¹⁶³ “If we had a digital equivalent of this text, [...] a digital edition in all its parts, [...] tagged, and that can be queried. Then yes, in that case everything could be considered data” (“[...] se avessimo per dire anche un equivalente digitale di questo testo, [...] un'edizione digitale in tutte le sue parti, [...] in modo che sia interrogabile, sia taggato. Allora in questi casi sì, tutto potrebbe essere considerato un dato”).

¹⁶⁴ “Onestamente no, [...] sono proprio materiali, ecco, non abbiamo per questo tipo di ricerca dei dati in senso stretto, in senso tecnico [...]”.

¹⁶⁵ “Non lo so nel senso che non sono abbastanza dentro al mondo tecnologico [...]”.

5.8.4 Spontaneous use of the word “data”

As mentioned before, we introduced the term “data” only towards the end of the interview, with questions 7 and 8. Interestingly, however, 12 researchers employed the term well before, in different contexts:

- 6 used it exclusively within the term “database” (“banca dati”);
- 2 referred to sensitive and personal data (“dati sensibili”, “dati personali”);
- 2 researchers referred to gathering data as part of their research;
- another 2 used it several times in different contexts.

5.9 Defining data

The eighth and final interview question asked: “More generally, what would you tell me if I asked you to define the word ‘data’?”¹⁶⁶.

5.9.1 Doubts and objections to the term “data”

Two of the interviewees who answered “yes” to question 7 above expressed nonetheless a certain difficulty with the term data. They stated that it is difficult to define, and that trying to understand what data is inevitably brings up more questions:

I know what [data] are until someone asks me to define them¹⁶⁷.

It is a complex question [...] I don't know if I'm answering your question or rather asking new ones¹⁶⁸.

Another researcher, who also answered “yes” to question 7, objected strongly to the use of the word, stating that “data” is too generic a term, and therefore useless. They added it is also reductive, as “data is the definitive answer ‘2 and 2 is 4’”, while real science means asking new questions; they added we should use the term “heuristics” instead¹⁶⁹. They also felt that the term was linked to a commodification of research, just like the term “products of research”.

In reviewing the literature, **we have encountered several times the idea that humanists find the term “data” especially problematic** (e.g., Hofelich Mohr et al. 2015; Edmond 2019). The reasons are usually very similar to the one expressed by our interviewee. As we have just seen, **this point did emerge from our interviews, but not as strongly as we would have**

¹⁶⁶ For the untranslated question in Italian, and how it compares to Thoegersen's, see [section 3.1](#).

¹⁶⁷ “[Un dato] so che cos'è finché qualcuno non mi chiede di definirlo”.

¹⁶⁸ “Sì, allora è una domanda in realtà complessa [...] non so se ti do una risposta a questa domanda o se pongo altre domande”.

¹⁶⁹ “[...] il termine ‘data’ è insufficiente perché ‘data’ è la risposta due più due fa quattro, quattro e basta quello che noi otteniamo non è quattro e basta è anche la premessa di un'altra domanda che è la vera scienza”.

expected. This may perhaps indicate that attitudes, within the arts and humanities domain, are shifting.

5.9.2 Statements on data from the project participants

It is now time to look at the definitions of data that emerged throughout the interviews¹⁷⁰. At this stage, I will concentrate on the statements researchers made about data across all interviews, rather than looking at each interviewee's point of view (for more on that, see [section 5.9.3](#) below).

Most researchers made at least 1 statement that in our view **restricts the definition of data**. In total, we counted 22 such statements. We offer a summary of the most interesting points below, from the most to the least frequent:

- **data are circumscribed and objective** (e.g., "I have this idea of data as something circumscribed, objective and definable, but I don't know if it's correct"; "data are single information items referring to a problem"; "data are the raw material of empirical research and become data when they can be reused")¹⁷¹;
- **interpretation and research results are not data** (e.g., "data is all the materials I have come in contact with except my interpretation, I would exclude that"; "I would not consider the book [we published] as data because it is a reworking, a synthesis and a presentation of known facts, we have not gathered new data"; "my results are not data, they are results I obtain from the data")¹⁷²;
- **methodologies and working notes are not data** ("I would separate methodology from data, otherwise the concept [of data] becomes too generic"; "I would not consider, for example, an annotation schema as data because it's a tool, not something I research")¹⁷³;

¹⁷⁰ I will consider here the answers to both question 7 and 8, as well as the remarks that, in some cases, researchers made after the end of the official interview.

¹⁷¹ "Ho idea del dato come qualcosa di più circoscritto oggettivo e definibile, però non so se è un'idea corretta"; "[...] il dato è il singolo item di informazione rispetto ad un problema"; "I dati sono la materia prima dell'osservazione empirica e sono dato nel momento in cui sono riutilizzabili cioè sono materia prima".

¹⁷² "Dati sono tutto il materiale che ho incontrato esclusa la parte di interpretazione mia, quella la escluderei"; "Del libro non considererei niente come dato perché in quel caso si tratta di rielaborazione, sintesi e presentazione [...] di cose già conosciute per cui non abbiamo raccolto dati nuovi"; "I miei risultati non sono dei dati, sono risultati che ho ricavato dai dati".

¹⁷³ "[...] io tenderei a separare la metodologia dal dato [...] a dare un po' di senso a questa parola che è iper generica"; "[P]er esempio uno schema di annotazione, ecco, non lo definirei forse dato perché non è che su quello io faccio della ricerca, è un materiale".

- **data are quantitative** (“[Data are] quantitative components we find during research, biographical data, precise dates”)¹⁷⁴.

Nonetheless, as we already know, interviewees did not shy away from offering their opinion on which research materials should be considered data. **Some of their statements below “open up” the definition of data considerably.** This is what emerged:

- **publications are data** (e.g., “a scientific article can be considered data, of course it can be considered as data”; “certainly, archival documents’ reproductions, their transcriptions, their editions [are data]”)¹⁷⁵;
- **methodology and notes are data** (e.g., “methodology is data; and even better if it is innovative compared to those used beforehand, to show it is indeed data, intellectual energy sources that were previously not considered”; “reading a passage according to a certain critical framework, as proposed in an essay or an article is data, assuming that is done according to a serious methodology: a sentence like ‘this is the best passage of Vergil’s poem’ is not data in my opinion”)¹⁷⁶;
- **interpretation and research results are data** (e.g., “the results or research can indeed be considered data”; “I understand data both as data emerged from research and as hypotheses”; “[...] new data, which we hope will emerge from our monograph”; “my judgment on the authenticity of a source can be data”)¹⁷⁷;
- **linguistic corpora are data** (e.g., “data are informative elements from a larger population that is homogenous”; “I can make a mistake in interpreting what is behind it and maybe you can interpret it better, but the linguistic phenomenon is documented and objective”)¹⁷⁸;
- **primary sources are data** (e.g., “data is what we start from and as such they can be materials of all kinds”; “data in the context of research are [...] all the primary

¹⁷⁴ “[Dati] sono tutte quelle componenti quantitative che si incontrano durante la ricerca: i dati biografici, magari anche date precise”.

¹⁷⁵ “Un articolo scientifico può essere considerato un dato, certo che può essere considerato come dato”; “sicuramente le riproduzioni dei documenti d’archivio, le trascrizioni di questi documenti e l’edizione di questi documenti [sono dati]”.

¹⁷⁶ “La metodologia è un dato, meglio se la metodologia è innovativa rispetto alle metodologie utilizzate fino ad ora per far vedere che sono dati, ovvero fonti di energia intellettuali, quelli che finora non venivano considerati”; “La lettura secondo un certo modello di critica letteraria di un passo così come è proposta in un saggio, in un articolo è un dato; posto che chiaramente sia condotta con una metodologia seria, una frase come ‘questo è il passo più bello del poema virgiliano’ per me non è un dato”.

¹⁷⁷ “[...] i veri e propri risultati della ricerca effettivamente sì posso essere configurati come data”; “Il dato io lo intendo sia come i dati emersi dalla ricerca quanto le ipotesi”; “novità, dati nuovi, che speriamo vengano fuori dalla nostra monografia”; “può essere dato il giudizio che io do sulla genuinità della fonte”.

¹⁷⁸ “Il dato è un elemento informativo di una popolazione molto più ampia ma omogenea e confrontabile”; “posso sbagliarmi ad interpretare cosa c’è dentro e l’interpreterete meglio voi però il fenomeno linguistico è documentato ed è oggettivo”.

materials we use”; “for us sources are the primary element [...] so the source itself can be considered data”)¹⁷⁹;

- **critically reconstructed texts and variants in an apparatus are data** (“I would claim that the text I have critically reconstructed within an edition is data”; “I would consider data mainly the text I am editing and also all the variants in my apparatus because they indeed are the collation data I am presenting to my readers”)¹⁸⁰;
- **software and ontologies are data** (“There is an entire school of software engineering that looks at software from an empirical standpoint, so there the data is the software, the code. Ontologies are of course data and are formalised according to other data”)¹⁸¹.

Two researchers even replied that **everything** is data:

In my opinion everything is data, everything I produce, handle, reuse, for me they are all data. Then it depends on the perspective one takes [...]¹⁸².

In my case they are all data, the first look I take at a new manuscript, what I decipher reading the first line of that manuscript, the reasoning on the *stemma codicum* to understand whether two manuscripts depend on a sub-archetype; everything I obtain from a serious, in-depth investigation is data, but it is a generic term, and as such it is useless¹⁸³.

Finally, we want to cite 2 attempts at defining data at a more abstract level:

Data is, let’s say, [...] an element that adds something new to knowledge compared to what was known before¹⁸⁴.

By data I would indicate, on the one hand, structured information that can carry an interpretation, communicating some precise knowledge, and, on the other, can be used by other researchers with

¹⁷⁹ “I dati sono quelli da cui noi partiamo e quindi possono essere materiali delle più diverse specie”; “Dati nel contesto della ricerca sono [...] tutti i materiali primari utilizzati per la ricerca”; “Per noi l’elemento fondamentale e primario sono le fonti, d’accordo, quindi già la fonte di per sé può essere considerata un dato”.

¹⁸⁰ “Mi verrebbe da dire il testo da me stabilito in un’edizione critica è un dato quello sì”; “Considererei dati sostanzialmente il testo che di cui faccio l’edizione e anche tutte le varianti che metto in apparato perché sono proprio dati di collazione che presento ai lettori”.

¹⁸¹ “C’è tutto un filone di software engineering che studia i software dal punto di vista empirico; quindi, lì il dato è appunto il software, il codice, quindi è un dato. Le ontologie sono dati, naturalmente, vengono formalizzati secondo dei dati”.

¹⁸² “Per me tutto è un dato, tutte le cose che produco, maneggio, riuso, per me sono tutti considerati come dati. Poi dipende un po’ dalla prospettiva in cui ci mettiamo [...]”.

¹⁸³ “Per me sono tutti dati, sono dati il primo sguardo che do a un manoscritto nuovo, sono dati quello che decifro leggendo la prima riga di quel manoscritto, sono dati i ragionamenti che faccio sull’albero stemmatico per definire se quei due manoscritti dipendono da un sub-archetipo; quindi, tutto ciò che io ricavo da un’indagine seria e approfondita è un dato, ma è un termine generico dato e quindi come tutti i termini generici non ci servono”.

¹⁸⁴ “Un dato diciamo è [...] un elemento che aggiunge qualcosa di nuovo alla conoscenza rispetto a quanto prima si sapesse”.

different methodologies and with aims that can be very different from those for which they had been collected¹⁸⁵.

5.9.3 Attitudes towards data among the project participants

We have just seen that, across the interviews, some researchers restricted the term “data” to something “circumscribed, objective and definable”, while others took a more inclusive view. Indeed, most participants seemed to go back and forth between these 2 positions.

Considering each interviewee’s answers in full, I weighed the different statements they had made and rated their overall opinion on data on a scale from 5 (very generic, “everything is data”) to 1 (very precise, “data are circumscribed and objective”). The results are shown in the table below.

Table 5.7: View on data on a scale from 5 (very generic) to 1 (very specific)

Rating	Definition of data	N. of researchers (tot. 19)
5	“everything is data”	2
4	very open, tends to include primary sources, interpretation, methodologies, and research results	4
3	open, tends to include either one among primary sources, interpretation, methodologies, research results	5
2	somehow restrictive, but can include either primary sources, critical texts, and/or textual variants	2
1	restrictive: data is circumscribed and objective	3
n/a	no reply or could not confidently assign a rating	3

Overall, **most researchers included several, if not all, research materials in their definition of “data”** (11), while a **minority (5) defined them rather precisely** as “information items”, “raw materials”, or “quantitative components”. Interestingly, the most restrictive definitions all seem to come from researchers belonging to the field of language and linguistics¹⁸⁶.

Two researchers recognised they had changed their minds, explicitly **broadening their definition of data during our conversation**. In one case, the interviewee gave a restrictive definition of data as “objective” and “raw”; later, after the end of the official interview, after reasoning on the concept of data in the context of open data, they acknowledged that a wider view may also be taken. The other researcher began by considering only research results as data, but then added primary sources to the definition:

¹⁸⁵ “Con dati intenderei degli insiemi strutturati di informazioni che possano sia essere portatori loro di una presentazione interpretativa, quindi possano da soli già comunicare una precisa conoscenza, dall’altro possano essere utilizzati da altri ricercatori con metodologie differenti per usi e scopi anche molto lontani e diversi da quelli per i quali sono stati raccolti”.

¹⁸⁶ For our division of the sample in macro-discipline see [section 3.2](#).

[The] materials I used could be defined as data. Not only the results, but the raw material. It came to mind while we were talking¹⁸⁷.

It is worth noting that nobody mentioned **interpretation and methodologies** at the beginning of the interview, when asked to list their research materials. However, at this stage, **6 researchers explicitly included them in their definition of research data**.

The reasons for this shift are unclear but it is reasonable to think that question 3c, which focused the interviewees attention on disciplinary-specific methodologies and their potential formalisation, had something to do with it. We might also hypothesise that the mention of “open data” at the start of question 7 prompted, in some cases, a comparison with the hard sciences and a desire to underline how methodologies play as much a role in the arts and humanities as in the hard sciences.

We have seen how **methodologies, or workflows**¹⁸⁸, are **usually excluded from the definition of data** (Directorate-General R&I 2021; Wilkinson et al. 2016). If, however, we consider them as research objects that can be “formalized”, “(semi-) manually captured” (Fenlon 2019), executed, and reused by other researchers in different contexts, then they surely must be included in our definition of data that need to be made FAIR.

5.9.4 Attitudes towards open access and open data in our sample

Some researchers within the group we have interviewed expressed concerns around:

- the use of article/book processing charges (APC/BPC) in open access publishing (1 researcher);
- the new rules around EU-funded projects, particularly the speed at which changes are being implemented and the imposition of open access for monographs, which limits researchers in their choice of a publisher for their work (3);
- the difficulty of more traditional, less methodologically innovative, research projects in accessing funding in the current landscape (3).

Others reported a positive attitude towards open data e open science, expressing:

- a willingness to share research data and a desire to “give back” to society the results of research (4);
- a desire for support from universities and public institutions, especially regarding research infrastructures, eliminating the need to rely on commercial third-party services (2);

¹⁸⁷ “[II] materiale utilizzato [...] potrebbe essere definito dato. Non solo il risultato, ma il materiale bruto. Mi è venuto in mente parlandone”.

¹⁸⁸ As we have seen in [section 2.4.2](#) we employ the two terms interchangeably here.

- concerns about traditional publishers protecting academic works excessively and in fact preventing the circulation of research results (2);
- a desire to see primary sources digitised and made available for research (2).

Across all interviews, we counted 18 statements that we categorised as positive, and 10 that we categorised as negative. We can therefore conclude that **positive attitudes towards open data and open science are prevalent among the participants to our study**. I will conclude by quoting 1 researcher who made an important point:

There can be a sense of fatigue for humanists, ‘gosh I have to share my data’, because to do that I have to follow a standardised schema. I [...] never make them available for the community so they can use them autonomously. It is extra work, and I feel we should understand that, if that is the case, all projects need a bit more workforce and even people with specific expertise. We have very small projects¹⁸⁹.

These points echo those made several times across the literature: that is necessary to **work on current evaluation practices to make data curation worthwhile**, and that universities and research bodies need to provide support to humanities researchers if we are to realise the FAIRification of research data.

¹⁸⁹ “[...] questo comporta anche un senso di fatica per gli umanisti ‘oddio devo mettere a disposizione i dati’ perché per mettere a disposizione i dati devi seguire uno schema standardizzato. Io stessa [...] non li metto mai a disposizione di una comunità che li può usare in una maniera autonoma. Questo è un aumento di lavoro io ho l’impressione che in quel caso bisognerebbe capire che tutti i progetti richiedono di un po’ di più di forza lavoro e anche di posti appositi del personale apposito. Noi abbiamo dei progettini minuscoli”.

6. Conclusions

The entire discussion around **what data is** might seem redundant or pointless to some. At the same time, stretching the definition of data to also include publications, workflows or indeed anything researchers work with – as some, including us, have done – may seem dangerously vague and ultimately useless.

Indeed, if we started adopting terminology like “open scholarship” (Tennant et al. 2019) or “FAIR digital object” (Directorate-General R&I 2018), then, perhaps, we could agree. But as long as we keep talking about “open science” and “open data”, and about the FAIRification of research data, we have to consider data as universal a concept as possible (Avanço, Balula et al. 2021, p. 22), one that also **includes all materials used and produced in humanities research**.

Otherwise, we really risk imposing on the arts and humanities “assumptions about how knowledge creation operates and communicates” (Tóth Czifra 2019, p. 3) that are too restrictive and that ignore how researchers operate in these disciplines. If we want to fruitfully apply FAIR data principles, then we need to start looking closely at how researchers work day-to-day, “going as deep as possible in research practices” and linking the definition of data “to the workflow of knowledge creation” (CO-OPERAS & Giglia 2020², p. 1).

The study described here has done just that, by interviewing 19 researchers within the department of Classical Philology and Italian Studies at the University of Bologna to **enquire on how they work, what sort of research materials they use and whether they consider them as research data**. It has, of course, important limitations: the sample of participants is small, and they all belong to 5 disciplinary areas¹⁹⁰. Ideally, it should be replicated on a larger scale, and should include other disciplines to paint a more precise picture of the situation.

Nonetheless, as described in [section 5.2](#), we have extrapolated from the interviews a list of 16 research materials that constitute the “building blocks” of research in the humanities, as far as our group of participants is concerned. They are:

- publications,
- digital representation of cultural objects,
- catalogues, databases and other search tools,
- ancient manuscripts and early printed books,
- events,
- unpublished materials,

¹⁹⁰ They are philology and literary criticism, language and linguistics, history of art, computer science, archival and library studies. For more on how we selected participants, please see [section 3.2](#).

- websites,
- software,
- documentation,
- digital infrastructures,
- archival documents,
- monuments, artworks and unique artifacts,
- personal data,
- corpora,
- standards,
- born-digital artifacts.

Whether we want to call them “data”, “materials”, or “resources”, if we are looking to apply FAIR principles within our disciplines, these are the type of research objects we need to start reflecting on and developing infrastructures for.

Publications emerged as the most important type of data in the humanities, in terms of research output, but also in terms of input, be it primary or secondary sources (see [section 5.2](#)). We can therefore conclude that, at least in the humanities, open access to scientific publications and open data policies are strictly interconnected.

In reviewing the literature, we have encountered more than once the idea that humanists find the term “data” especially problematic. Edmond, for example, argues that it is too vague, applying to “inputs, results, or intermediary research outputs” and that its “slippery overdetermination” is “problematic indeed” (Edmond 2019, p. 6).

In our own interviews, we avoided the term “data” until the 2 final questions, using the expression “research materials” instead (see [section 3.1](#)). However, we found that **the term “data” was not particularly problematic for our interviewees**, with 14 (of the total 19) responding that they indeed work with data. All in all, only 3 researchers expressed unease with or resistance to the term (see [section 5.8](#)).

There certainly is confusion on the definition of data, as reported elsewhere (CO-OPERAS, Bertino, Tóth-Czifra 2020; CO-OPERAS, Giglia 2020). **Most of our participants included several, if not all, materials they use in research in their definition** (11), while a minority (5) defined them reductively as “information items”, “raw materials”, or “quantitative components”. And while nobody of course mentioned **interpretation and methodologies** as “research materials”, by the end of the interview 6 researchers had explicitly included them in their definition of data. The reasons for this shift remain unclear, but we have attempted an explanation (see [section 5.8](#)).

We have seen that methodologies, or workflows, are usually excluded from the definition of data (Directorate-General R&I 2021; Wilkinson et al. 2016). However, when we asked researchers at FICLIT whether their **work is based on a precise methodology, recognised**

across the field, the vast majority immediately replied positively. Even philologists and literary critics, which we could argue are more “traditional”, claim they have an extremely precise methodology (see [section 5.4.2](#)). Although we are a long way away from workflows that are “explicit [...] documented and, therefore verifiable” (Edmond 2019, p. 15), our analysis suggests that researchers might be ready to reflect on how to “characterize humanities workflows” and to “identify how such characterizations can be made useful” (Fenlon, 2019, p. 512).

Regarding aspects of data management, such as the use of documentation and metadata ([section 5.4.1](#)), potential copyright or privacy issues ([section 5.6](#)), storage and preservation habits ([section 5.7](#)), our results mostly confirm what emerged from previous studies (see [section 2.6](#)). One notable exception concerns the willingness to share research data with colleagues: **we found collaboration to be extremely important for our interviewees**, both in the shape of informal sharing (9/19) and actual teamwork (12/19) (see [section 5.5.1](#)).

As for the attitudes towards open science and open data, they are mostly positive across our pool of researchers ([section 5.9.4](#)). But, as stated by a handful of interviewees, and as emerged clearly from the literature (CO-OPERAS, Bertino and Tóth-Czifra 2020; Edmond 2019; Tóth Czifra 2019), it is necessary to **work on current evaluation practices, to make data curation worthwhile**, and to support humanities researchers in the process of making research more findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable.

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